

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Report on Suitability maps for grapevines and supplementary crops for actual and future climatic conditions at macro scale

SPOKE 6 – PRIMARY AGROINDUSTRY

DELIVERABLE D1.1 and DELIVERABLE D1.2

Version history

No.	Date	Details	Author(s)
0.1	08/12/2024		Marta Debolini, Serena Marras, Valentina Mereu, Luca Mercenaro, Emanuele Serra, Donatella Spano, Antonio Trabucco,
0.1	02/07/2025	Pedological and topographic suitability	Uta Biino, Federico Amari, Eliana Tonelli, Vanna Maria Sale
0.1	30/09/2025	Climatic and Total suitability	Amin Ghezavati nezhad, Massimiliano Bordini, Claudia Meisina

This document is part of the project NODES which has received funding from the MUR – Missione 4, Componente 2, Investimento 1.5 – Creazione e rafforzamento di “Ecosistemi dell’innovazione”, costruzione di “leader territoriali di R&S” – del PNRR funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU with grant agreement no. ECS00000036

Contents

GLOSSARY.....	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	5
INTRODUCTION.....	5
SELECTION OF INDICATORS.....	6
MULTICRITERIA ANALYSIS FOR LAND SUITABILITY AT THE MACRO-SCALE.....	8
ASSESSMENT OF RELATIVE WEIGHT FOR THE SELECTED INDICATORS	9
RESULTS FOR THE SARDINIAN CASE STUDY.....	12
DATA SOURCES.....	12
SUITABILITY IN THE CURRENT CLIMATE CONDITIONS	13
SUITABILITY IN THE FUTURE CLIMATE CONDITIONS.....	15
SUITABILITY MAPS FOR ACTUAL CLIMATIC CONDITIONS AT MACRO-SCALE	24
LAND UNIT MAP.....	25
APTITUDE FOR SPECIFIC USES: LAND SUITABILITY CLASSIFICATION	27
VITICULTURAL SUITABILITY OF THE OLTREPÒ PAVESE – MACROSCALE	28
SOIL SUITABILITY FOR VITICULTURE - MACROSCALE.....	29
TOPOGRAPHIC SUITABILITY FOR VITICULTURE – MACROSCALE	32
CLIMATIC SUITABILITY FOR VITICULTURE – MACROSCALE IN THE CURRENT CLIMATIC CONDITION.....	34
CLIMATIC SUITABILITY METHODOLOGY	34
CLIMATIC SUITABILITY FOR VITICULTURE – FUTURE SCENARIOS.....	37
ACTUAL CONDITIONS CLIMATIC SUITABILITY RESULT.....	37
ACTUAL CONDITIONS CLIMATIC SUITABILITY MAP.....	38

FUTURE SCENARIOS CLIMATIC SUITABILITY RESULTS	38
FUTURE SCENARIOS CLIMATIC SUITABILITY MAP	40
TOTAL SUITABILITY FOR VITICULTURE.....	42
TOTAL SUITABILITY FOR VITICULTURE FUTURE SCENARIOS	43
ACTUAL CONDITION TOTAL SUITABILITY RESULT	43
FUTURE SCENARIOS TOTAL SUITABILITY RESULTS	44
ESTIMATION OF TOTAL SUITABILITY FOR GRAPEVINES IN OLTREPÒ PAVESE THROUGH A DATA-DRIVEN METHODOLOGY.....	48
TOTAL SUITABILITY RESULTS FOR ACTUAL AND FUTURE SCENARIOS	51
FUTURE SCENARIOS.....	53
CONCLUSIONS.....	56
REFERENCES.....	56
APPENDIX: SPATIAL ASSESSMENT OF PINOT NOIR IN OLTREPÒ PAVESE: ANALYSIS OF THE DOC/DOCG AREA AND POTENTIAL EXPANSION IN THE MOUNTAINOUS OLTREPÒ REGION	58

GLOSSARY

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework - NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, and demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable D1.3 is based on the analysis of bioclimatic, soil and topographic indicators assessed at spatial scale on the two pilot areas of Sardinia Region and Oltrepò Pavese, in order to obtain a synthetic map of suitability for vineyards in the current climatic conditions. Bioclimatic specific indicators have been acquired at a fine spatial scale (2,2 km), from the analysis developed on the frame of the RM8 and described on the D8.3.

INTRODUCTION

CMCC is collaborating on the Flagship Project VINO part of NODES Spoke 6 by providing bioclimatic information for climate change impact analyses on vineyards or other cultivations characterized by high spatial and temporal resolution. Bioclimatic indicators are derived using atmospheric variables from climate projections, based on dynamic downscaling of regional climate models produced by CMCC.

Agricultural land suitability is determined by combining crop requirements and soil and other environmental attributes. Assessing how well the properties of a land unit align with the demands of specific land use by farming activities results in its suitability. Thus, 'suitability' quantifies the degree to which the characteristics of a parcel of land align with the requisites of a particular crop (FAO, 1976). The objective of the work is to integrate bioclimatic indices with soil and topography parameters to develop a GIS-based vineyard suitability analysis referring to a specific production target. To our knowledge, few studies have been realized until now combining different bioclimatic indices, pedological and topographical criteria and land use information to assess the land vineyard suitability. The method is based on a multi-criteria evaluation (MCE), and considering the FAO classification the study area has been classified into five classes based on its suitability: S1 – very suitable, S2 - suitable, S3 - moderately suitable, N1 - temporarily non suitable and N2 - permanently non-suitable.

SELECTION OF INDICATORS

The set of selected indicators is listed in Tab.1 with a specific description for each one. The selection of indicators started with an extensive bibliographic analysis to map the most used and established bioclimatic indicators for the study of areas suited to viticulture. In the second phase, the list of indicators has been modified, contextualizing the usefulness and representativeness of the indicators to the study area in which they would be applied. To assess the land suitability at the current and future climate conditions, the bioclimatic indicators were specifically assessed acquiring historical series of climatic data (last 30 years) available at 2 km resolution for the whole Italy (CMCC projections), and subsequently for projections at 2 km resolution under future climate conditions.

To characterize the most suitable topography, we have considered as indicators elevation, slope and aspect (defining together the amount of sunlight that particular area receives throughout the day). As soil data, we have acquired as variable: soil texture, soil organic carbon, pH, soil depth and electrical conductivity.

On the whole pool of indicators, we propose to apply some basic statistical analysis in order to identify possible correlation among variables, and thus their overlapping in terms of data content and trends. In the case that two or more indicators are strongly correlated, we will consider the possibility of reducing their number to a relevant subset with reduced data noise. In this sense, we propose applying an approach of data reduction, that is a subsetting of the possible variables based on the assessed correlations.

Tab.1: list and description of the whole set of available indicators

Clima			
Indicatore	Descrizione	Formula	Referenza
Cool night Index	Is a thermal index based on the night temperature during the ripening period (September in the Northern Hemisphere (NH))	$T_{min}(\text{sept})$	Tonietto and Carbonneau, 2004
Huglin Index	Is a thermal index based on degree days, i.e. on the concept of heat accumulation. This index is used to grapevines during the growing period to guarantee a complete and adequate ripening. Each grape variety requires a certain amount of heat accumulation for optimal ripening to occur	$\sum_{\text{April}}^{\text{Sept}} \frac{(\bar{T} - 10)(T_{max} - 10)}{2} \times k$	Huglin, 1978
Winkler Index	Is the sum of GDDs with a base temperature of 10°C. It provides information on the accumulation of heat during the growing season.	$\frac{31/10}{01/04} (\frac{T_{max} + T_{min}}{2} - 10)$	Amerine and Winkler 1944 Jorge Tonietto and Alain Carbonneau, 2004
Frost Free Days (FDD)	It is used to determine growing season length; it is the period between the last frost (temperatures below 0°C) in spring and the first frost in fall.	Number of frost-free days	Magarey et al. 1998
Dryness index	It assesses soil water availability by providing information on water stress conditions.	$\sum_{\text{April}}^{\text{Sept}} (W_0 + P - T_v - E_s)$	Riou et al., 1994; Tonietto and Carbonneau, 2004
Hydrotermic Index	It is an index that combines the effect of air humidity (through precipitation) and temperature during the growing season. It allows us to study the influence of temperature and precipitation on the grape yield and wine quality and to assess the risk of grape exposure to certain diseases such as mildew. this is a characteristic number, which measures the water supply for vegetation, and determines the possibility of rainfed viticulture.	$\sum_{\text{April}}^{\text{Aug}} (\bar{T} \times P)$	Branas et al., 1946;
Growing Season Precipitation Index (GSP)	It provides the general suitability used in climate zoning for viticulture that accumulates precipitation during the growing season. All daily GDD totals less than zero are set equal to zero.	$\sum_{01.04}^{31.09} P$	Blanco-Ward et al., 2007
NH, HHH, LHH	This method enables quantification of thermal limitation by low temperatures, when normal hours are useless because they are sub-optimal (LHH), and by high temperatures, when normal hours are useless because they are supra-optimal (HHH), respectively expressed as a complement to 1 for the NHH value.	$NHH = \frac{(2 \times (T_d - T_b)^n + (T_0 - T_b)^n - (T_d - T_b)^{2n})}{(T_0 - T_b)^{2n}}$	Mariani et al. 2012
BEDD	The Biological Effective Degree-Days index was developed by after observing that plant growth and phenological development respond to temperature in a nonlinear fashion and finding potential limitations to the standard WI and HI approaches. As such, the BEDD has three adjustments: (1) the interval of effective heat summation is considered between 10°C (base temperature) and 19°C (upper threshold); (2) a latitude adjustment to account for an increasing day length effect (the same as HI); and (3) a diurnal temperature range adjustment (DTRadj, upward if the DTR is >13°C and downward if <10°C)	$\sum_{\text{April}}^{\text{Oct31}} \min\{(\max\{([T_{max} + T_{min}]/2) - 10, 0\}), 9\} \times DTR_{adj} \times K$ where $DTR_{adj} = \begin{cases} 0.25[DTR - 13], & [DTR] > 13 \\ 0, & 10 < [DTR] < 13 \\ 0.25[DTR - 10], & [DTR] < 10 \end{cases}$ where K is an adjustment for latitude/day length ²	Gladstones (1992)
Soil			
Indicatore	Descrizione		
Depth of rooting zone	The zone between the surface and the effective rooting depth.		
pH	It is a measure of the acidity or alkalinity of the soil. A pH value is actually a measure of hydrogen ion concentration.		
Soil texture	Soil texture is a summation of proportions of sand, silt and clay content. Soil texture is a very stable characteristic that influences soil biophysical properties. The soil texture is associated with soil porosity, which in turn regulates the water holding capacity, gaseous diffusion and water movement that determines the soil health.		
Electrical conductivity	Soil electrical conductivity (EC) measures the ability of soil water to carry electrical current. Electrical conductivity is an electrolytic process that takes place principally through water-filled pores. Cations and anions from salts dissolved in soil water carry electrical charges and conduct the electrical current. In agriculture, EC has been used principally as a measure of soil salinity;		
Soil organic matter	Soil organic matter is the fraction of the soil that consists of plant or animal tissue in various stages of decomposition. Soil organic matter contributes to soil productivity in many different ways.		
Topography			
Indicatore	Descrizione		
Elevation	The vertical distance of a point or level on or affixed to the surface of the Earth measured from mean sea level.		
Exposure	Topographic exposure is a variable that represents the degree of shelter afforded to a location.		
Slope	Slope gradient is the angle of inclination of the soil surface from the horizontal.		
Land cover			

Multicriteria analysis for land suitability at the macro-scale

A Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) approach was selected for the development of the viticultural suitability map with the aim of integrating the main factors relevant to grapevine cultivation. The structure of the map was thus divided into two levels: the first level includes the macro-factors (climate, soil, topography), while the second level incorporates the individual indicators belonging to each macro-category, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig.1: Macro-category

For each selected indicator, it is possible to identify a range of values corresponding to the different suitability classes from the existing literature, considering several classes ranging from 0 (low suitability) to 1 (high suitability). The values from 0 to 10 represent a "suitability score", and these values need to be combined to obtain a final synthetic suitability index. The reference values can be taken from the existing literature, but they need to be contextualized for the selected production and the specificity of the case study. Most of the current studies apply a homogenous weight for each indicator, but in most cases, this does not correspond to the field reality, as some factors tend to have a stronger importance on suitability than others. For this reason, we propose to improve a weighting method to combine the indicators in a synthetic index. The flowchart of the method is represented in Fig.2.

Fig.2: Flowchart of the proposed methodology at macroscale

As a first approach, we propose applying for an Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP). AHP is a decision-making approach employed for prioritization and decision-making using multiple criteria. AHP is designed as a system to support optimal decision-making, particularly for complex circumstances with a hierarchical structure (Saaty 2008, 1990, 1980). In the AHP method, criteria are compared with others to obtain a final relative preference expressed as a numerical value. The AHP method is used in combination with the GIS tool to solve the problem of inconsistency in expert opinions by assigning relative importance or weight to each criterion and level and considering it in a suitability analysis. The first step to applying an AHP method has been to prepare and submit a questionnaire for local experts to acquire their vision about 1) the suitability classes for each indicator and 2) the relative weight of each indicator. All the answers will be processed through to apply specific weight to each indicator.

Assessment of relative weight for the selected indicators

To establish the relative importance of the variables, a pairwise comparison questionnaire was distributed using the CONAVI (Convegno Nazionale di Viticoltura) 2024 mailing list. The questionnaire was sent to a total of 130 addresses, and 13 responses were received. However, three of these responses were excluded due to the lack of clarity in the respondents' answers. A total of 10 questions were accepted for analysis, all of which were from academia.

1	Equal importance
3	Moderate importance
5	Strong importance
7	Very strong importance
9	Extreme importance
2,4,6,8	Intermediate values

Extreme	Very strong	Strongly	Moderate	Equal	Moderate	Strongly	Very strong	Extreme
9	7	5	3	1	3	5	7	9

The accepted responses were statistically examined to determine their consistency by following the following steps:

1. Creation of the pairwise comparison matrix
2. Calculating consistency ratio

If the value of Consistency Ratio is smaller or equal to 10%, the inconsistency is acceptable. If the Consistency Ratio is greater than 10%, we need to revise the subjective judgment.

The statistically consistent ratings were aggregated together using geometric means to determine the general matrix from which to calculate the final weights.

Among the 10 responses analyzed, 3 were valid for the macro factors level (Lev.1), 3 for the climate level (Lev.2), 3 for the soil level (Lev.2), and 3 for the topography level (Lev.2), as shown in Fig.3

Macrofattori	0.03	0.17	0.19	0.21	0.02	0.14	0.07	0.12	0.12	1.26
Clima	0.15	0.14	0.27	0.16	0.18	0.03	0.05	0.13	0.05	0.18
Suolo	0.05	0.18	0.40	0.28	0.10	0.08	0.11	0.11	0.12	0.59
Topografia	0.12	0.12	0.12	2.14	0.43	0.00	0.26	0.05	0.00	0.19

The integration of these judgments, carried out by geometric mean, led to the determination of the following weights:

1° LEVEL	CATEGORY	WEIGHT (%)	WEIGHT
Macrofactors	Climate	51.77	0.52
	Soil	36.37	0.36
	Topography	11.86	0.12

2° LEVEL	CATEGORY	VALUE	POINTS	SUITABILITY CLASS	WEIGHT (%)	OVERALL WEIGHT
Climate	Cool night Index	12-14	1	S1	11.1	5.73%
		14-18	2	S2		
		6-12/18-25	3	S3		
		<6; >25	4	N1		
			5	N2		
	Huglin	2100-2400	1	S1	16.3	8.45%
	1800-2100; 2400-2700	2	S2			

		1500–1800; 2700–3000	3	S3			
		1200–1500	4	N1			
		<1200; ≥ 3000	5	N2			
	Frost Free Days	>200	1	S1	11.9	6.17%	
		180–200	2	S2			
		160–180	3	S3			
		140–160	4	N1			
			5	N2			
	Dryness Index	50-(-100)	1	S1	42.5	22.03%	
		(-100)-(-200)	2	S2			
		<-200;50-150	3	S3			
		>150	4	N1			
			5	N2			
	BEDD	1600–1800	1	S1	18.1	9.39%	
		1400–1600; 1800–2000	2	S2			
		1200–1400; 2000–2200	3	S3			
		1000–1200	4	N1			
		<1000; >2200	5	N2			
	Soil	Depth	>100	1	S1	17.3	6.31%
			80-100	2	S2		
60-80			3	S3			
40-60			4	N1			
<40			5	N2			
pH	6.1–6.8	1	S1	8.3	3.01%		
	5.4–6.0; >6.8	2	S2				
	4.5–5.3	3	S3				
	< 4,5	4	N1				
		5	N2				
Texture	Clay loam /Sandyloam/ Loam	1	S1	34.0	12.37%		
	Sandy clay loam / Silty clay loam	2	S2				
	Loamy sand/Sandy clay Silty clay/Silt Loam	3	S3				
	Clay/Silt/San d	4	N1				
		5	N2				
CE	<2	1	S1	10.3	3.76%		
	>2;<4	2	S2				

		>4; <8	3	S3	30.0	10.92%
		>8	4	N1		
			5	N2		
	SO	2-3	1	S1		
		1-2	2	S2		
		3-5; <1	3	S3		
		>5	4	N1		
	5	N2				
Topography	Aspect	S/SE	9	S1	50.5	5.93%
		SW/E	7	S2		
		Flat/W/NE	5	S3		
		NW/N	1	N1		
			0	N2		
	Slope	2-15	1	S1	50.5	5.93%
		0-2;15-30	2	S2		
		>30	3	S3		
			4	N1		
			5	N2		

Fig.3: Macro factors levels

Results for the Sardinian case study

DATA SOURCES

The recent advancement in the very high-resolution climate dataset represents a significant breakthrough in our capacity to analyze local atmospheric dynamics, their interaction with complex topography and shorelines, and their spatial and temporal evolution under climate change conditions. This enhanced data availability enables more precise assessments of how climatic variability influences land suitability for viticulture. This study exploits very high-resolution climate datasets developed in the framework of the Highlander project (Bottazzi et al., 2024) to support impact assessments across several key sectors. Specifically, climate data for the reference period (1981-2010) were obtained from the dynamical downscaling of ERA5 Reanalysis (Hersbach et al., 2020) at a ~2.2km resolution through the Regional Climate Model COSMO5.0_CLM9 (Rockel et al. 2008, Adinolfi et al., 2023; Raffa et al., 2021). For the future climate variations, covering both 2021-2050 and 2036-2065 periods under RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 IPCC scenarios, we used the output data (Raffa et al., 2023) of simulations run with the Regional Climate Model COSMO5.0_CLM9 forced by the CMCC-CM global model (Scoccimarro et al., 2011).

Regarding the adopted IPCC scenarios, the RCP 4.5 scenario denotes a stabilization pathway in which anthropogenic radiative forcing reaches and remains at 4.5 W m⁻² above pre-industrial

levels by the end of the 21st century, without exceeding this threshold at any time. This scenario assumes the implementation of climate policies that limit greenhouse gas emissions, leading to a stabilization of atmospheric concentrations and associated radiative forcing without an overshoot trajectory. The RCP 8.5 scenario represents a high-emission trajectory in which anthropogenic radiative forcing reaches 8.5 W/m² above pre-industrial levels by the end of the 21st century. It assumes continued high greenhouse gas emissions in the absence of significant climate mitigation policies, resulting in substantial increases in atmospheric concentrations and associated climate impacts. The atmospheric variables used for the assessment of bioclimatic indicators are open source and available on the CMCC Data Delivery System (CMCC DDS). Soil data were obtained from the European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC) (Ballabio et al., 2016, 2019; European Soil Data Centre (ESDAC); Hiederer, 2013a, 2013b; Panagos et al., 2012, 2022) and from (Schillaci et al., 2025) at ~1km resolution, while the input data to compute topographic indicators were obtained from the Tinitaly Digital Elevation Model at 10m resolution (Tarquini et al., 2007, 2012; Tarquini & Nannipieri, 2017).

SUITABILITY IN THE CURRENT CLIMATE CONDITIONS

In the following section, we report the results obtained for the macro-area of the Sardinia Region. The results are presented first as the single factors of suitability (soil suitability, topographic suitability and bioclimatic suitability), and then, present the map integrating the three macro-factors, obtaining the synthetic map of the overall land suitability for vineyard cultivation, following the multi-criteria method already presented in the previous paragraphs.

Fig.4a and 4b: Maps of the topographic suitability (a, around 85meters of spatial resolution) and soil

suitability (b, around 1 km of spatial resolution) for the Sardinia Region.

As we can see from fig.4a, topography plays a very relevant role in the Sardinia region, as many internal areas are too steep to accommodate crops. On the other hand, soil suitability seems stable in the whole region, having high values overall. In this case, the reason is probably related also to the spatial resolution of the soil map, which is at 1 km, not allowing to distinguish locally articulated differences. An analysis at higher resolution, if detailed pedological maps were available, could allow to refine this analysis.

As indicated in the previous paragraphs, bioclimatic suitability is evaluated based on 5 different indicators, overlapped following the propose weighting scheme presented beforehand. The resulting map has spatial resolution of 2.2 km. As we can see from fig.5, most of the surfaces in the Sardinia region result as very suitable for vineyards cultivation, in terms of bioclimatic conditions. The most suitable sub- regions are located in the northern and eastern part, whereas the internal mountain areas are less suitable.

The weighted overlapping of the soil, topographic and bioclimatic variables resulted on the synthetic map of general land suitability for vineyards cultivation in Sardinia (Fig.6).

Fig.5: Bioclimatic suitability for the current climate

Fig.6: Overall land suitability

SUITABILITY IN THE FUTURE CLIMATE CONDITIONS

Bioclimatic indicators

Bioclimatic indicators computed both for the reference period (1981–2010) and projected climate scenarios (RCP 4.5 and 8.5 for 2021–2050 and 2036–2065) are displayed in Figure 7. All the bioclimatic indices showed a similar pattern, which basically follows the regional topographic profile. In fact, thermal accumulation-based indices, such as BEDD and HI, showed the highest values corresponding to the flat areas, due to warmer temperatures and higher seasonal heat accumulation. In contrast, hilly and mountainous areas were mostly characterized by lower values. However, as shown in Figure 7, values related to those indices were projected to increase in the future across all scenarios and time frames, especially for 2036–2065 in RCP 8.5. Also, CNI, which is the minimum temperature in September, and FFD, which is the sum of days between the last frost in spring and the first frost in fall, basically showed patterns that are shaped by the regional orography, with both indices showing the lowest values in the mountainous areas. Regarding DI, the only water availability-based index, it showed lower water availability in flat areas while more positive values are mainly concentrated in higher elevation areas.

The area-weight distributions of climatic indices were directly compared with the actual vineyard distribution (SAAR, 2008). The results indicate that most of the existing vineyards were located within the S1–S2 suitability classes for thermal indices such as BEDD (~1600–1800 °C), suggesting

optimal thermal conditions considering this index. Regarding HI, current vineyard distribution was more strongly associated with S2 and S3 classes, with values mainly ranging from ~2200 to ~3000 °C, suggesting sub-optimal thermal conditions with respect to this index (mainly S2 and S3 classes). Similarly, the CNI distribution showed values between ~14 to ~20 °C, corresponding to the S2 – S3 classes, which represents moderately cool nights favorable for color and aroma development in grapes. In contrast, DI showed both negative and positive values (-50 to 100 mm), suggesting a variability in Sardinian vineyards in terms of water availability. However, such values are associated with optimal conditions for viticulture. Similarly, FFD index exhibited a narrow distribution around 270–275 days (class S1).

Fig 7: Maps of bioclimatic indices computed for reference period (1981-2010) and both 2021-2050 and 2036-2065 periods under RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 IPCC scenarios

Maps of indices reclassified according to suitability values are displayed in Figure 8. Concerning HI and BEDD, both of which are based on thermal accumulation, the two indices showed

substantial differences. Biologically Effective Degree Days exhibited a more positive trend, with flat areas being highly suitable (9; S1 class) in the reference period. However, suitability in these areas was projected to decrease, especially under the 2036-2065 RCP 8.5 scenario, in favor of higher elevation zones, especially in the north of the region. In contrast, HI reclassified maps revealed a more pessimistic view of the viticultural suitability of the Sardinia region. With respect to BEDD, the spatial pattern was more complex and clearly shows lower suitability values corresponding to flat areas while better conditions were concentrated in hilly and mountainous zones, showing an almost opposite behavior. Considering future scenarios, especially for RCP 8.5, HI low suitable values were projected to spread across the island, while the best conditions for viticulture were projected to be mainly concentrated on the more elevated zones. Even if both those indices are based on temperature, the differences between them may explain the discrepancy in these results. Huglin Index calculation summarizes the daily mean and maximum temperatures from April to September, with a latitude-based correction factor (Huglin, 1978), while BEDD developed to overcome potential limitations of HI and Winkler Index, integrate a heat summation interval (10-19 °C), a diurnal temperature range adjustment, and a latitude adjustment (as HI) and is calculated from April to October. In this regard, HI calculations produced very high values, especially under future scenarios, which are not suitable for viticulture. For the reference period, CNI showed the lower suitability values in the flat zones, which were projected to get more unsuitable going to future scenarios. Regarding DI, despite Figure 5 showing a general trend that highlights drier conditions for future, especially in lower altitudes areas, the suitability values exhibited a pattern where values are favorable for flat areas in general, and becoming unsuitable in higher latitude zones, even in the future, apart from some zones in the south. Frost Free Days showed highly suitable values across all scenarios.

Fig.8: Reclassified bioclimatic indices

Bioclimatic, Soil, and Topographic Suitability

Considering that soil and topographic indicators were considered constant across time, bioclimatic analysis may need some attention to understand possible future changes. Maps of bioclimatic suitability for present and future climate scenarios are represented in Figure 9a.

Fig.9: **a)** Bioclimatic and **b)** Multicriteria suitability maps

For the reference period, a total of 17,396 km² (75.0%) was considered to be highly suitable (S1), 5,366.8 km² (23.1%) being suitable (S2), and 435 km² (1.9%) being moderately suitable (S3). Moving to future scenarios, the analysis showed a general trend in which the areas highly and moderately suitable for viticulture (S1 and S3) tend to decrease in favor of suitable areas (S2). For the 2021–2050-time frame, S1 areas were projected to decrease from 17,396 km² to 13,840 km² (59.7%) and 12,599 km² (54.3%) for RCP 4.5 and 8.5, respectively. At the same time, S2 areas tended to increase, moving from 5,366 km² (23.1%) for the reference period, to 9,186 (39.6%) in RCP 4.5 and 10,334 (44.5%) in RCP 8.5. The trend became more evident for the 2036-2065 period, in which S1 areas were projected to decrease to 10,676 km² (46.0%) in RCP 4.5 and to 9,457 km² (40.8%) in RCP 8.5. For the same period, S2 areas were projected to increase to 12,410 km² (53.5%) for RCP 4.5 and to 13,655 km² (58.9%) for RCP 8.5.

Bioclimatic suitability areas and percentages across classes are reported in Table 5. In terms of anomalies (future-present), as shown in Table 6, the areas in S1 showed a rate of change with a minimum of -20.4% in RCP 4.5 2021-2050 to a maximum of -45.6% in RCP 8.5 2036-2065. At the same time, S2 area anomalies went from a minimum increase of +71.2% in RCP 4.5 2021-2050 to a maximum increase of 154.4% in the 2036-2065 scenario.

Observing bioclimatic suitability maps, considering both climate scenarios, several regional variations in how climate change is projected to affect viticultural suitability across Sardinia are reported, which are more pronounced in RCP 8.5. In particular, the southern part of the island was expected to experience a shift from highly suitable (S1) to suitable (S2) conditions under future climate scenarios. Similarly, part of the central-western island was also projected to

undergo a downgrade from S1 to S2, basically following the elevation pattern and involving zones with limited elevation (<200m), as shown in Figure 1. Furthermore, some central regions were also likely to shift from S1 to S2. Some central areas, which historically fall within the suitable class (S2), may benefit from future climatic conditions and shift into the highly suitable class (S1), suggesting a local improvement in viticultural potential. In contrast, part of the central-eastern of the island, were projected to experience a decrease in suitability, with some areas shifting from S1 to S2, while other parts will benefit from the new conditions. Again, also in these zones the decrease in suitability mostly concerned zones with lower altitude, while the opposite behavior primarily involved higher elevation zones. In the southeastern and northeastern coastal areas, current S1 zones were generally expected to decrease in suitability, shifting to S2 under both RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 scenarios. In northern Sardinia, the eastern coastal areas were projected to undergo a similar decline in suitability, while the north-central coast may see a relative improvement. Finally, in some northwestern regions, a general decrease in suitability was projected, with transitions from S1 to S2 being the predominant trend. Figure 10 shows a distribution plot of the classes with respect to mean elevation across climate scenarios and time frame.

Fig.10: Bioclimatic suitability in relation to the mean elevation across climate scenarios and time frame

The plot demonstrates that, across scenarios, S1 zones were projected to move to higher altitudes while an opposite pattern characterizes S2 zones, which will probably move from higher to lower altitudes. Apart from the weight assigned to the indicators, some consideration of the indices that contributed to these changes can be given. For example, as shown in Figure 4, FFD index ($w_2=0.12$), did not contribute to any change, because it has been found to be highly suitable in all scenarios and time frames. In contrast, the CNI index ($w_2=0.11$) indicated suitable (S2) conditions across most of the study area, and highly suitable (S1) conditions in the highest part of the island, except for coastal and low altitude zones in the southeast. In terms of future conditions, CNI characterised moderately suitable (S3) class in most of the study areas, and suitable (S2) class in the highest zone of the island. Dryness Index had an important influence on the analysis ($w_2=0.43$). Particularly, DI values showed a high suitability (S1) class at the lowest altitudes and moderately suitable (S3) class and permanently not suitable (N2) conditions going to the highest elevation zones. Biologically Effective Degree Days and HI showed the highest spatial variability in the area. Particularly, HI, showed the most severe conditions for viticulture in the future scenarios, with most of study areas becoming unsuitable (N2) under future conditions. However, this index had a relatively limited relevance in the analysis ($w_2=0.16$). Regarding the BEDD Index ($w_2=0.18$), it showed a majority of high suitability (S1 class) zones for the reference period, especially for low altitude zones, while for future conditions the same areas will become less suitable in favor of an increasing suitability for higher altitude areas.

An overlay analysis between the areas currently occupied by vineyards (SAAR, 2008) and the bioclimatic suitability maps is presented in Table 2 in terms of absolute surface (ha) and percentages, to better assess the results with respect to actual vineyard distribution

Table 2 – Vineyard area distribution in relation to bioclimatic suitability classes results across climate change scenarios.

	Reference		2021-2050				2036-2065			
			RCP 4.5		RCP 8.5		RCP 4.5		RCP 8.5	
	ha	%	ha	%	ha	%	ha	%	ha	%
S1	21688	91.3	10702	45.1	9916	41.8	6206	26.1	5321	22.4
S2	2045	8.6	13046	54.9	13832	58.2	17541	73.9	18427	77.6
S3	15	0.1	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
N1	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
N2	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0

As shown in Table 2, more than 91% of the current vineyard distribution was placed in areas classified as S1. However, projections indicated that in the future, the areas currently cultivated with vineyards will probably shift to lower suitability classes. In particular, for the 2021-2050 period, around 41-45% of the current vineyard area was expected to remain in highly suitable S1 class, while for the 2036-2065 period, only 22-26% was projected to remain highly suitable (S1), with most shifting into the less suitable S2 class. Topographic and soil suitability maps are represented in Figure 11.

Fig.11 Topographic and soil suitability

Soil suitability showed a dominance of S1 across the area, with a total of 23,265 km², which corresponds to 98.8% of the area, which will heavily influence multicriterial results. Soil indicators, especially Texture, Electrical Conductivity and Organic Carbon, were mostly favorable in terms of vineyard suitability, giving a high score for the soil suitability map, and consequently for the multicriteria suitability maps. Regarding topographic suitability, results showed the prevalence of S3 class, with a total of 9,568 km² (39.7%), followed by S2 with 8,107 km² (33.6%) and S1 class with a total of 4,813 km² (20.0%). Soil and topographic suitability areas are reported in Table 3.

Table 3 – Soil and topographic suitability areas.

	Soil		Topography	
	km ²	%	km ²	%
S1	23,266	98.8%	4,814	20.0%
S2	278	1.2%	8,107	33.6%

S3	12	0.1%	9,569	39.7%
N1			1,630	6.8%
N2				

Multicriterial Suitability

Maps of bioclimatic suitability under the multi-criteria approach for present and future climate scenarios are shown in Figure 10b. For the reference period, a total of 20,585 km² (88.7%) was classified as highly suitable (S1), 2,532 km² (10.9%) as suitable (S2), and 80.1 km² (0.3%) as moderately suitable (S3). No areas were identified as temporarily not suitable (N1) or permanently not suitable (N2) under any scenario. Looking at future projections, the analysis revealed a general trend of stability, with highly suitable areas (S1) remaining predominant across all scenarios. Specifically, during the 2021–2050-time frame, S1 areas were projected to increase to 21,281 km² (91.7%) under RCP 4.5 and to remain high at 20,842 km² (89.8%) under RCP 8.5. At the same time, S2 areas showed a minor decrease compared to the reference period, dropping to 1,895 km² (8.2%) in RCP 4.5 and 2,332 km² (10.1%) in RCP 8.5. S3 areas resulted marginal in both scenarios, with values below 0.2%. This trend remained consistent or became slightly more pronounced in the 2036–2065 period, where S1 areas measured 21,015 km² (90.6%) under RCP 4.5 and 20,188 km² (87.0%) under RCP 8.5, the only scenario where S1 decreased compared to the reference period. Simultaneously, S2 areas increased slightly to 2,171 km² (9.4%) and 3,001 km² (12.9%), respectively. Multicriteria suitability areas and percentages are reported in Table 9. In terms of anomalies (future–present), the area classified as highly suitable (S1) showed a slight positive variation, with a maximum increase of +3.4% in RCP 4.5 for 2021–2050, and a maximum decrease of -1.7% in RCP 8.5 for 2036–2065. Conversely, S2 areas showed more dynamic behavior, ranging from a minimum decrease of -25.2% in RCP 4.5 (2021–2050) to a maximum increase of +18.6% in RCP 8.5 (2036–2065). The S3 class areas were projected to remain nearly negligible in all future scenarios (Table 10). These results were primarily driven by climate factors, which account for 52% (w1=0.52), by soil factors that influence the analysis for 36%, and by topographic indicators, which had a relatively small effect (12%) on the final map. Given the almost equal distribution of topographic suitability among classes, it is evident that the multicriterial suitability map is primarily driven by climate and soil indicators. In particular, the predominance of the S1 class for soil suitability gave a “mitigation effect” to the effect of climate anomalies between scenarios. The only scenario in which the S1 class was projected to decrease in terms of area in comparison to the reference conditions was the RCP 8.5 2036–2065, showing a different behavior compared to the bioclimatic trend, in which the S1 class substantially decreases its area across scenarios and time.

SUITABILITY MAPS FOR ACTUAL CLIMATIC CONDITIONS AT MACRO-SCALE

ERSAF developed the “Suitability maps for actual climatic conditions at macro-scale” from the Land Unit Map (UdT) produced at semi-detailed scale within this project. This map builds on ERSAF’s previous territorial analyses, specifically the “I suoli dell’Oltrepò pavese” at 1:50 000 (plain and lower-hill soils) and the “Carta dei suoli della Lombardia” at 1:250 000 (regional overview at lower resolution), which covers the entire Oltrepò Pavese area.

Areas mapped at 1:250 000 were grouped according to physiographic attributes (primarily elevation and slope), substrate type, the presence and intensity of hydro-geological instability, and predominant land use. These classifications were then enriched by additional soil profiles drilled and described in the hilly and mountainous zones, to deepen understanding of the soils defining each UdT and of the properties that influence their suitability for vine cultivation and other crops. From each profile’s genetic horizons, recorded in the field by macromorphological description, disturbed soil samples were collected and subjected to laboratory analyses for key physicochemical parameters (fine earth fractions, pH, total and active calcium carbonate, total carbon and organic carbon, cation-exchange capacity and exchangeable bases, electrical conductivity, total nitrogen, assimilable phosphorus, and heavy metals such as copper and nickel).

Profile selection considered the variability of previously mapped Soil Typological Units (UTS) and current land use. Woodland areas, which extensively cover the higher elevations of the Oltrepò Pavese, were excluded, as well as the plains and lower hills, which had already been surveyed at a semi-detailed scale. The new data enabled the definition of nine additional UTS, covering most of the non-wooded hilly and mountainous territory. The plains, lower hills, and forested areas are described by existing Soil Typological Units (UTS) mapped at 1:250,000 scale, while for the plains, more detailed information is available thanks to the 1:50,000 scale map.

Field campaigns conducted within the framework of the NODES project, initially via boreholes and subsequently by excavating and describing the profiles mentioned, revealed a notable uniformity in soil characteristics. This homogeneity originates from the marl- and clay-rich lithology of the parent material and from the region’s natural susceptibility to hydro-geological instability, exacerbated over time by agricultural abandonment and ongoing climate change. These factors drive frequent erosion, resulting in continually rejuvenated (young) soils.

Observed soils show little to no evidence of pedogenetic development or differentiation from their parent material, clustering into a limited range of texture classes, reaction (pH), carbonate content, and other quality-influencing properties such as useful depth, cation exchange capacity and base saturation. Consequently, physiographic factors overwhelmingly determine the land’s suitability for various uses, outweighing pedological criteria.

In drafting the UdT map - which forms the basis for the evaluation of soil aptitude for viticulture or alternative land uses - the structure of the 1:250 000 pedological map was preserved. In the mountainous areas of the Oltrepò Pavese, newly acquired data have been integrated, whereas for the northern plains, lower hills, and those mountain sectors already surveyed, the existing UTS framework has been retained.

LAND UNIT MAP

The Land Unit Map, as shown in the map below, features a hierarchical structure for describing the territorial context in which the UdT are located and which they represent. At the top level is the “Physiographic Domain,” subdivided into one or more geographically defined “Territorial Domains.” Each UdT is assigned based on its location and, where justified by morphological variation, may recur across different domains. In such cases, physiographic elements that collectively define the physical framework of the territory take precedence in grouping the units.

The following table shows a brief description of the land units

TERRITORIAL AREA	TERRITORIAL AREA DESCRIPTION	LAND UNIT	STU N.	STU NAME
Physiographic area - Po River floodplain				
Pavia section of the Po River floodplain	Po River unicorsal bed, with islands and channels, embanked with large floodplain area, at elevations between 50 and 80 m (mean elevation 60 m) and with mean slope less than 1%, with abundant traces of relict channels and paleovalvements. Sandy sediments, sometimes with gravels and silts, noncalcareous to calcareous in west-east transition. Arable land (maize) predominates there, with large areas affected by poplar cultivation; forests (oak-harps) on about 5 % of area. between 12 °C and 14 °C and yearly rainfall between 650 and 750 mm.	1	601	VRR1
		2	267	ISN1

Physiographic area - Plain of Apennine pertinence				
Voghera plain	Oltrepò Pavese plain, with recent and post-glacial alluvium of the Po and streams of Apennine origin, with hanging riverbeds in S-N direction, located at elevations between 50 and 200 m (mean elevation 80 m) and mean slope of about 1%. Calcareous, predominantly silty sediments. Arable land occupies 75% of the area, marginal presence of vineyards (5%). The yearly average temperature is between 13°C and 15°C; yearly rainfall ranges between 650 and 750 mm.	3	247	GOD1
		4	524	GUD1
		5	503	SGD1
Voghera and Stradella terraces	Terraces in relief on the plains and terraced valley bottoms of the main streams on the border between the plains and hills of Oltrepò Pavese, at elevations between 60 and 400 m (average elevation 150 m) and average slope slightly above 10%). Calcareous, sandy and silty sediments. About 40% of the area planted with vines, 35% with arable crops (wheat and corn), and a little more than 10% is wooded. The yearly average temperature is between 13°C and 15°C; yearly rainfall is between 650 and 750 mm.	6	462	RG11
		7	559	TUG1
Physiographic area – Apennine hills				
Versa valley low hills	Hilly areas around Val Versa, between 70 and 700 m (average elevation about 200 m), with low to moderate slope (average slope 17%) and subparallel drainage in SE-NW, S-N and NE-SW directions. The substrate consists mainly of turbiditic successions (argillites, calcarenites, marls, chalks and limestones) and there is widespread geomorphological instability. Vineyards are more than 50 % widespread followed by arable land (wheat) and deciduous forests. Vineyards are more than 50 % widespread followed by arable crops (wheat). Rainfall is low (less than 800 mm per year on average) and average yearly temperatures is between 12°C and 15°C.	8	1388	LV_001
		9	1382	CM_001
		10	1387	FL_001
		11	1389	RG_001
		12	1386	CM_005
		13	1385	CM_004
Low inland hills east of the Staffora valley	Hilly areas and steeply sloping slopes east of the Staffora Valley and south of the Versa Valley, at elevations between 100 and 600 m and mainly around 300 m, with medium to high slopes (average slope 20%). The substrate is predominantly marly or calcarenitic, sometimes clay-shale (Chaotic). About 50 percent of the area is occupied by deciduous (downy oak) or mixed forests with the presence of black pine or lodgepole pine; followed by arable land (crop rotation), and sparse vineyards. Disturbed areas occupy about 30 percent of the area. Rainfall is low (less than 800 mm per year on average) and average yearly temperatures are between 12°C and 15°C.	14	1390	FL_SPS2
		10	1387	FL_001
		15	1400	CM_fv
		16	1381	CL_001
		17	1401	CM_fv
		18	1402	CM_fv
		19	1403	RG_qv
High hills and transition to mid-mountain	Oltrepò hillsides south to Varzi, between 200 and 900 m (mostly between 400 and 600 m). Slopes are variable, ranging from moderate to steep (average slope 30%), and widespread and intense hydrogeological disruption persists. Drainage is subparallel and oriented in an E-W direction. The substrate is calcarenitic, marly, and calcareous, and the predominant land use is deciduous forest (chestnut and oak) with less widespread grassland and arable (wheat), alternating with natural areas. Rainfall is low (less than 800 mm per year on average) and average yearly temperatures are between 10°C and 14°C.	20	1404	RG_qv
		21	1385	CM_004
		17	1401	CM_fv
		18	1402	CM_fv
		22	1389	RG_001
		23	1385	CM_004
		24	1386	CM_005
		25	1385	CM_004
		26	1385	CM_004
		27	1405	CM_fv_
		28	1406	RG_ca
29	1386	CM_005		
Alta valle Staffora montana	Hilly and mountain slopes of the Staffora and Tidone Valleys, at elevations between 400 and 1700 m (mainly between 500 and 1100 m), with high gradient (average slope 37%) and widespread and intense disruption. The substrate is calcareous with calcarenites, argillites, marls, and with patches of Caotic. Forests, deciduous, mixed and coniferous, to arable land (wheat)	30	1407	FL_ca
		31	1384	CM_003
		18	1402	CM_fv
		32	1408	CL_qv
		33	1389	RG_001
		34	1384	CM_003
Physiographic area - Submountain and mountainous Apennines				

<p>predominate, alternating with sparse meadows or natural areas. Rainfall averages between 700 and 1100 mm yearly, increasing regularly according to the N-S gradient; average temperatures are between 8°C and 13°C.</p>	35	1386	CM_005
	36	1386	CM_005
	37	1385	CM_004
	38	1386	CM_005
	39	1386	CM_005
	40	1389	RG_001
	41	1384	CM_003
	42	1389	RG_001

The UdT are defined according to the territory's physiographic and climatic characteristics, as well as its principal land-use types. The soils characterizing each UdT are described both by their general attributes—such as effective rooting depth and any limitations, texture, permeability, drainage, plant-available water capacity, etc.—and by their functional horizons, i.e. horizons with similar properties in terms of the key ecological and agronomic functions they perform, including carbon sequestration, water filtration and contaminant reduction, biodiversity reservoir, regulation of water flows, nutrient cycling, and supporting crop production. Functional horizons correspond to the genetic horizons recognized within each Soil Typological Unit (UTS); when two or more genetic horizons of the same pedogenetic origin exhibit sufficiently similar properties, they are aggregated into a single functional horizon.

Notably, UdT10 and UdT18 illustrate the map's domain overlap: UdT10 represents intermontane valley-floor soils and occurs in both the Versa valley hills and the inner Staffora valley hills, while UdT18 spans from the lower Staffora hills up into its higher mountain valley. Similarly, UdT17—found in the lower Staffora hills—has been extended to include a small polygon in the upper hill zone transitioning into mid-mountain, based on physiographic and pedological similarity.

APTITUDE FOR SPECIFIC USES: LAND SUITABILITY CLASSIFICATION

Land Suitability Classification (LSC) method was developed by the FAO in the 1970s to provide a tool for assessing land aptitude for a specific use, taking into account both the economic dimension (returns relative to the investments made) and the sustainable use of environmental resources, defined as practices that can be maintained over an extended period without causing significant or permanent degradation of resource quality. LSC categorizes land as suitable or unsuitable according to the five classes described below:

- S1 Highly Suitable** - land having no significant limitations to sustained application of a given use, or only minor limitations that will not significantly reduce productivity or benefits and will not raise inputs above an acceptable level;

- S2 Moderately Suitable** - land having limitations which in aggregate are moderately severe for sustained application of a given use; limitations reduce productivity or benefits and increase the interventions needed to overcome them and the overall advantage to be gained from the use, although still attractive, will be appreciably inferior to that expected on Class S1 land;
- S3 Marginally Suitable** – land having limitations which in aggregate are severe for sustainable application of a given use and so reduce productivity or benefits, or increase required inputs, that this expenditure will be only marginally justified;
- N1 Currently Not Suitable** - land having limitations which may be surmountable in time but which cannot be corrected with existing knowledge at currently acceptable cost; the limitations are so severe as to preclude sustained successful use of the land in the given manner;
- N2 Permanently Not Suitable** - land having limitations which appear so severe as to preclude any possibility of successfully sustained use of the land in the given manner.

The application of the method requires the development of a model capable of classifying the environmental indicators considered most influential on the potential development of the crop under evaluation within the target area.

The LSC approach has been adopted to assess the suitability of the Oltrepò Pavese region for viticulture, according to the methodology described below.

VITICULTURAL SUITABILITY OF THE OLTREPÒ PAVESE – MACROSCALE

For the evaluation of territorial characteristics determining viticultural suitability, the analysis was based on the model proposed by the University of Sassari and the CMCC (Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change). This model, inspired by the Land Suitability Classification (LSC) and previously applied at micro-scale on four sites monitored by the University of Pavia in the Oltrepò Pavese area, considers three macro-factors: climate, soil, and topography. Each factor is assessed individually and then combined into an overall suitability score through algebraic summation, based on a relative weight assigned to each component.

The evaluation model adopted includes a table in which, for each of the three macro-factors, a set of parameters is considered. Each parameter is described in value classes that correspond to the suitability classes defined by the Land Suitability methodology. Additionally, each parameter is assigned a weight representing its relative importance within the macro-factor, which is then translated into a corresponding score. The sum of all parameter scores within each macro-factor equals one.

The tables related to the “soil” macro-factor—and, to some extent, also to “topography”—have been modified by ERSAF to better reflect the specific characteristics of the Oltrepò Pavese territory. Climatic suitability will not be addressed here, as its assessment is carried out by UNIPV, which will also produce the overall suitability evaluation by integrating the pedological and topographical suitability analyses developed by ERSAF.

SOIL SUITABILITY FOR VITICULTURE - MACROSCALE

To develop the soil suitability at the macroscale, ERSAF started from the Soil Typological Units (UTS) that characterize the Land Unit Map (UdT), considering the following indicators:

- **Useful depth** for root development; this includes also non-pedogenized material (horizon C) provided it does not impose physical or chemical constraints to root penetration;
- **Soil Reaction**, measured as pH in water;
- **Texture class** of the fine earth ($\Phi \leq 2$ mm), defined based on the proportions of its fractions (sand, silt, and clay) according to the USDA soil texture triangle;
- **Total carbonates**, expressed as CaCO_3 ;
- **Organic matter** (SO).

All parameters, except for the useful depth, were considered as weighted averages over the 0–100 cm soil thickness or over the useful soil depth if this is shallower. The useful depth value, however, refers to the soil as a whole.

The evaluation table originally proposed by CMCC and UNISS was adjusted (see table below), following consultations with viticulture experts, to better fit the characteristics of the pilot area. These changes involve the ranges of suitability classes and replacing the EC parameter (electrical conductivity), which doesn't effectively discriminate in Lombardy, with the Total Carbonates indicator, which is far more relevant. High levels of total carbonates can be potentially limiting and affect rootstock selection and vineyard management practices.

The weighting of the indicators was also changed, assigning greater weight to the two inherent parameters (useful depth and texture), compared to the other three (pH, CaCO_3 , organic matter), which can be managed through soil amendments and corrective measures.

The weight assigned to the first level of analysis, relating to the integration of macro-factors, has been also modified based on the specific characteristics of the study area. Specifically, the weight of the topography has been increased and that of the soil has been reduced, while the weight previously assigned to climate has been only minimally reduced, remaining the predominant, as shown in the table below.

1° LEVEL	CATEGORY	WEIGHT	WEIGHT
Macro-factors	Climate	50	0.5
	Soil	15	0.15
	Topograph	35	0.35

The following table shows weights and relative scores of the indicators adopted to assess the macro-scale suitability of Oltrepò Pavese for viticulture respect to the soil macro-factor as modified by ERSAF

MACRO FACTOR	SOIL QUALIFIER	CLASS RANGE	POINTS	SUIT CLASS	WEIGHT QUAL.
SOIL	Useful Depth cm	> 80	1	S1	29
		60 - 80	2	S2	
		30 - 60	3	S3	
		≤ 30	4	N1	
			5	N2	
	pH pH unit	5.3-8.0	1	S1	14
		5.0-5.2 8.1-8.3	2	S2	
		4.4-4.9 8.4-8.5	3	S3	
		< 4.4; ≥ 8.5	4	N1	
	Texture USDA class	FAFSAF	1	S1	29
		FLAFSA	2	S2	
		SFALFLASA	3	S3	
		SL	4	N1	
	total CaCO ₃ %	≤ 20	1	S1	15
		20 - 35	2	S2	
		35 - 40	3	S3	
> 40		4	N1		
SO %	≥ 2	1	S1	13	
	1 - 2	2	S2		
	1 - 0,6	3	S3		
	0,4 - 0,6	4	N1		
	< 0,4				

Considering that the UTS indicators are connected to the UdT, and thus to the shapefile polygons of the corresponding shapefile (Land Unit Map), it was necessary to generate a raster for each indicator using the “Polygon to Raster” function within the “Conversion Tool” of the ArcGIS Pro software.

The sequence of operations carried out is outlined below:

1. For all Soil Typological Units (UTS): weighted average over the 0–100 cm depth for each soil qualifier listed in the modified table, except for effective soil depth;
2. Assignment of the calculated average values to the corresponding polygons in the Land Unit Map (UdT);
3. Conversion from polygon to raster for each considered indicator, using the “maximum_area” option, which assigns to each cell the value of the polygon with the largest area within it;
4. Resampling of the "soil" rasters (170 x 170 m cells) to the cell size of the “topographic” rasters (20 x 20 m);
5. Reclassification of the individual raster layers obtained, assigning numerical scores from the “points” field to the value classes according to the criteria outlined in the table presented above;
6. Sum of the reclassified rasters “usable depth”, “texture”, “total CaCO₃”, “pH” and “SO” using the “Raster calculator” function, assigning to each qualifier the weight within the soil macro-

factor (field "WEIGHT QUAL." in the table above), i.e. multiplying each raster by the corresponding weight divided by 100, so that their sum corresponds to 1; classification of the resulting raster using the following threshold values: $S1 \leq 1$; $S2 \leq 2$; $S3 \leq 3$; $N1 \leq 4$.

The result was the raster displayed in the figure below, which represents the soil suitability for viticulture in the Oltrepò Pavese area at macroscale.

Considering only the soil macro-factor, the Oltrepò Pavese is suited to viticulture, with 70% of the territory falling into the S2 "moderately suitable" class, and 30% into S3 "marginally suitable" class. Classes N1, "currently unsuitable", and N2, "permanently unsuitable", are not present.

The most limiting factors, significantly influencing the assignment to the lower suitability class (S3) are the useful soil depth and the texture class. The former is often affected by the presence of layers, whether pedogenized horizons or parent material resulting from substrate alteration,

which can be massive and highly compacted, or, less frequently, by continuous, cemented lithoid substrate. The latter reflects the widespread clay-dominated textures in the Oltrepò area, where this fraction is almost always associated with high silt content. Together, these characteristics negatively influence effective porosity and the amount of water available to plants. Although these soils have high water reserves, most water is held too tightly for the root systems to effectively utilize it.

TOPOGRAPHIC SUITABILITY FOR VITICULTURE – MACROSCALE

The following table shows weights and relative scores of the indicators adopted to assess the macro-scale suitability of Oltrepò Pavese for viticulture respect to the topography macro-factor as modified by ERSAF.

MACRO FACTOR	TOPOGR. QUALIFIER	CLASS RANGE	POINTS	SUIT CLASS	WEIGHT S. Q.
TOPOGRA PHY	Elevation m.s.l.m.	120 - 400	1	S1	33,33
		400 - 600	2	S2	
		600 - 900	3	S3	
		≤ 120; > 900	4	N1	
			5	N2	
	Aspect °N	SE (112,5 - 157,5)	33,33		
		S (157,5 - 202,5)			
		E (67,5 - 112,5); SW (202,5 - 247,5)			
		NE (22,5 - 67,5); W (247,5 - 292,5)			
		NW (292,5 - 337,5); N (337,5 - 22,5)			
	Slope %	2 - 20	33,33		
		20 - 35			
		35 - 45			
		≤ 2; > 45			

With respect to the indicator weighting table presented in chapter “Assessment of relative weight for the selected indicators”, adjustments were made to the classification of both altitude and slope, while the internal scoring within the macro-factor, specifically the relative weighting of the three parameters, remained unchanged.

The sequence of operations carried out for the assessment of topographic suitability is as follows:

1. Starting from the Lombardia_dem 20x20 Digital Terrain Model (DTM), the “slope_percentage” and “aspect” rasters were generated using the respective tools available in the Spatial Analyst Tools / Surface toolbox;
2. Classification of the same DTM according to the elevation ranges defined in the table above, to obtain the “elevation” raster;
3. Reclassification of the “slope” and “aspect” rasters according to their respective classes defined in the table;
4. Summation of the reclassified “elevation,” “slope,” and “aspect” rasters using the “Raster Calculator” function, assigning each the same weight (33%), i.e., by multiplying each raster by 0.33;

5. Classification of the resulting raster using the following threshold values: $S1 \leq 1$; $S2 \leq 2$; $S3 \leq 3$; $N1 \leq 4$; $N2 \leq 5$.

The result was the raster shown in the figure below, which represent the topographic suitability for viticulture in the Oltrepò Pavese area.

As with the soil, the topography macro-factor also shows that the Oltrepò Pavese area is suited to viticulture. The first two classes, S1 ("Highly Suitable") and S2 ("Moderately Suitable"), cover approximately 40% of the surface area, nearly reaching 60% when including class S3 ("Marginally Suitable"). The N classes, represented here only by class N1 "Temporarily Unsuitable," cover approximately 40% of the surface area. This represents a significant increase compared to their absence observed in the soil suitability assessment alone, confirming the greater influence of physiographic factors over pedological ones in determining the area's viticultural potential.

The most limiting topographical factors for viticulture are altitude, including lowland areas (elevation less than or equal to 120 m above sea level) and mountainous areas (elevation greater than 900 m above sea level), and slope when it exceeds 45%. Conversely, aspect classes are quite uniformly distributed and tend to penalize the lowland areas, where the issue is not so much unfavorable exposure but rather the absence of exposure due to low altitude and flat terrain. It is also noteworthy that most of the steepest slopes have historically been covered by forest, thus not available for agricultural use. While this makes them unavailable for viticulture, it concurrently improves their stability, thereby reducing the risk of hydrogeological instability.

CLIMATIC SUITABILITY FOR VITICULTURE – MACROSCALE IN THE CURRENT CLIMATIC CONDITION

This section assesses the climatic suitability of the Oltrepò Pavese region for viticulture at the macro scale. Climatic suitability was evaluated under both actual and future climate scenarios using five bioclimatic indices relevant to grapevine development. The objective is to identify climatically favorable and constrained areas, and to assess how projected climate change may alter these patterns over time.

CLIMATIC SUITABILITY METHODOLOGY

To evaluate the climatic suitability of the Oltrepò Pavese region for viticulture under current climate conditions, we applied a GIS-based Multi-Criteria Evaluation (MCE) methodology. This process followed the suitability classification structure adopted by References for this regional viticulture analysis. The analysis focused on five bioclimatic indicators selected based on viticulture-specific relevance and scientific literature:

- 1-Cool Night Index (CNI)
- 2-Huglin Index (HI)
- 3- Frost Free Days (FFD)
- 4-Dryness Index (DI)
- 5-Biologically Effective Degree Days (BEDD)

Each raster layer was first reclassified into five suitability classes, ranging from S1 (very suitable) to N2 (permanently not suitable), based on predefined threshold values. These thresholds were informed by viticultural climatology and adapted to the characteristics of Northern Italy. Reclassification was performed using QGIS's Raster Calculator tool with Boolean logic to avoid overlapping conditions.

The climatic suitability assessment was based on five bioclimatic indicators selected for their relevance to grapevine development: Cool Night Index (CNI), Huglin Index (HI), Frost Free Days (FFD), Dryness Index (DI), and Biologically Effective Degree Days (BEDD). Each indicator was reclassified into suitability classes (S1–N2) according to threshold values derived from viticultural literature and adapted to the Oltrepò Pavese case study.

Climatic suitability was assessed using the same approach adopted in Sardinia. The table below presents the value ranges, classification thresholds, corresponding suitability classes, and weights for each climatic indicator, referred to Oltrepò Pavese.

2° LEVEL	CATEGORY	VALUE	POINTS	SUITABILITY CLASS	WEIGHT (%)	OVERALL WEIGHT
Clima	Cool night Index	12-14	1	S1	20 %	10.4%
		14-18	2	S2		
		6-12/18-25	3	S3		
		<6; >25	4	N1		
			5	N2		
	Huglin	2100–2400	1	S1	20 %	10.4%
		1800–2100; 2400–2700	2	S2		
		1500–1800; 2700–3000	3	S3		
		1200–1500	4	N1		
		<1200; ≥ 3000	5	N2		
	Frost Free Days	>200	1	S1	20 %	10.4%
		180–200	2	S2		
		160–180	3	S3		
		140–160	4	N1		
			5	N2		
	Dryness Index	50-(-100)	1	S1	20 %	10.4%
		(-100)-(-200)	2	S2		
		<-200;50-150	3	S3		
		>150	4	N1		
			5	N2		
BEDD	1600–1800	1	S1	20 %	10.4%	
	1400–1600; 1800–2000	2	S2			
	1200–1400; 2000–2200	3	S3			
	1000–1200	4	N1			
	<1000; >2200	5	N2			

Climatic indicator weights (CNI, HI, FFD, DI, BEDD) follow the literature-based methodology proposed by CMCC; any adjustments to the climatic weights were suggested by CMCC during the last meeting. ERSAF implemented the pedological and topographic components and, drawing on in-house expertise and external specialist guidance, adapted their weights to the Oltrepò Pavese context. The table below presents the value ranges, classification thresholds, suitability classes, and weights for each indicator.

Following reclassification, the indicators were weighted according to their importance in influencing viticultural performance. Each of the five selected climatic indicators was assigned an equal weight reflecting its relative influence on viticultural conditions, based on expert-derived importance scores reported in the CMCC methodological framework. The final weights used in the overlay were:

- 1-Dryness Index (DI):20%
- 2-Huglin Index (HI): 20%
- 3- Biologically Effective Degree Days (BEDD): 20%
- 4-Frost Free Days (FFD): 20 %
- 5-Cool Night Index (CNI): 20 %

The choice of an equal value of 20% weight for each climatic index is related to calibrate the model to the actual distribution of grapevines in Oltrepò Pavese area. In fact, the weights calibrated for Sardinia produced unrealistic N1 patches in Oltrepò Pavese. Given the region's known viticultural vocation, we adopted equal 20% weights for DI, HI, BEDD, FFD, and CNI to: (i) avoid those artifacts, and (ii) give a balanced, context specific importance to the five climate drivers, since no single indicator is expected to dominate here. This setting proved the most consistent result for the current-climate assessment, according to this modeling framework.

To facilitate interpretation, the final raster was discretized into five classes using fixed threshold ranges:

- Class1: S1 (Highly Suitable): 0.00 – 1.00
- Class2: S2 (Suitable): 1.01 – 2.00
- Class3: S3 (Moderately Suitable): 2.01 – 3.00
- Class4: N1 (Currently Not Suitable): 3.01 – 4.00
- Class5: N2 (Permanently Not Suitable): > 4.00

This classified raster provides a spatially explicit representation of climate-based suitability for viticulture, and was later integrated with pedological and topographic layers to compute total suitability.

CLIMATIC SUITABILITY FOR VITICULTURE – FUTURE SCENARIOS

This section evaluates the climatic suitability of the Oltrepò Pavese region for viticulture under projected future climate conditions. The analysis was performed at the macro scale using four climate scenarios:

1-RCP 45 (2021–2050)

2-RCP 45 (2036–2065)

3-RCP 85 (2021–2050)

4-RCP 85 (2036–2065)

The methodological framework was identical to that used for the baseline assessment, ensuring full comparability between present and future conditions.

ACTUAL CONDITIONS CLIMATIC SUITABILITY RESULT

The resulting climatic suitability map for the Oltrepò Pavese region demonstrates that a substantial proportion of the territory falls under moderately and marginally suitable classes for viticulture under current climatic conditions. GIS analysis of the final climatic raster indicates the following distribution:

S1 (Highly Suitable): **0.00%**

S2 (Suitable): **43.42%**

S3 (Moderately Suitable): **56.58%**

N1 (Currently Not Suitable): **0.00%**

N2 (Permanently Not Suitable): **0.00%**

According to the modeling framework, the majority of the Oltrepò Pavese currently falls within S3 (Marginally Suitable; 56.58%), with the remaining area classified as S2 (Suitable; 43.42%). No areas are mapped as S1 (Highly Suitable), N1 (Currently Not Suitable), or N2 (Permanently Not Suitable). In this study, we adopt the FAO-style interpretation whereby S1, S2, and S3 are all suitable classes, while N1 and N2 are unsuitable.

This distribution suggests that sites with comparatively balanced thermal regimes and adequate frost-free periods tend to occupy the S2 (Suitable) category, while more than half of the territory

remains in S3 (Marginally Suitable), reflecting moderate but manageable climatic constraints. The lack of N1 areas indicates that, at the current scenario, climatic restrictions are not severe enough anywhere to preclude viticulture outright. Overall, these results emphasize the value of targeted adaptation and site-specific practices, particularly across S3 and at the margins of S2, to enhance the viticultural potential of the Oltrepò Pavese under present climate conditions.

ACTUAL CONDITIONS CLIMATIC SUITABILITY MAP

Actual conditions show that the entire study area falls into the moderately suitable or marginally suitable classes: **S2** (Moderately Suitable): **43.42%** and **S3** (Marginally Suitable): **56.58%**. There are no areas classified as S1 (Highly Suitable), N1 (Currently Not Suitable), or N2 (Permanently Not Suitable).

FUTURE SCENARIOS CLIMATIC SUITABILITY RESULTS

The analysis of climatic suitability under future scenarios indicates a significant shift in the distribution of viticulturally potential for the Oltrepò Pavese region. Contrary to previous, more severe projections, the area largely retains 100% suitability, primarily distributed across the S2 and S3 classes.

Future scenarios (RCP 45 and RCP 85 for both 2021–2050 and 2036–2065) demonstrate a clear trend towards lower overall suitability, specifically a reduction in the S2 class and a corresponding

increase in the S3 class. The total suitable area (S2 + S3 classes) remains 100% across all projections, indicating a maintenance of potential, however at a reduced level of quality.

Scenarios	S2	S3
Actual	43.42%	56.58%
ClimaticsuitabilityRCP45_21_50	42.70%	57.30%
ClimaticsuitabilityRCP45_36_65	12.06%	87.94%
ClimaticsuitabilityRCP85_21_50	26.83%	73.17%
ClimaticsuitabilityRCP85_36_65	15.08%	84.92%

This transition indicates that while under Actual climatic conditions viticulture benefits from a large portion of suitable (S2) zones, projected climate change will largely shift this potential towards the moderately suitable (S3) class, particularly in the later period (2036–2065).

Crucially, the absence of N1 and N2 across all four scenarios suggests that viticulturally potential is maintained throughout the region.

FUTURE SCENARIOS CLIMATIC SUITABILITY MAP

Climatic Suitability RCP 45 (2021-2050):

Climatic Suitability RCP 45 (2036-2065):

Climatic Suitability RCP 85 (2021-2050):

Climatic Suitability RCP 85 (2036-2065):

TOTAL SUITABILITY FOR VITICULTURE

This section presents the integrated suitability assessment based on the combination of climatic, soil, and topographic conditions. The total suitability represents a synthetic index of viticultural potential, reflecting all environmental constraints together. Maps were generated for both actual and future climate conditions to support comparative planning and regional land management decisions.

The total suitability map was developed by integrating the three analyzed macro-factors: climate, soil, and topography. Each macro-factor was represented by its own suitability raster derived from the reclassification and weighting of individual indicators, as defined in the methodological framework of the project.

Each of these macro-factor rasters was first calculated by applying specific weights to the selected indicators within that category (e.g., Huglin Index for climate, soil texture for pedology, and slope for topography). Once the reclassified and weighted layers were prepared for each macro-factor, the three resulting rasters were combined into a single suitability map.

The integration was performed using raster combination, where each macro factor raster was multiplied by its relative weight, specifically calibrated for Oltrepò Pavese area and summed:

Climatic Suitability: 50% → 0.5

Soil Suitability: 15% → 0.15

Topographic Suitability: 35% → 0.35

This produced a continuous raster representing the composite suitability score, which was then reclassified using the suitability classification scheme adopted and refined by references for this project:

Class1: S1 (Highly Suitable): 0.00 – 1.00

Class2: S2 (Suitable): 1.01 – 2.00

Class3: S3 (Moderately Suitable): 2.01 – 3.00

Class4: N1 (Currently Not Suitable): 3.01 – 4.00

Class5: N2 (Permanently Not Suitable): > 4.00

This reclassification allowed the identification of discrete suitability zones aligned with references categories, facilitating map interpretation and integration with land planning tools. The same methodology was replicated across multiple climate scenarios to ensure consistency in evaluating potential changes in viticultural suitability.

TOTAL SUITABILITY FOR VITICULTURE FUTURE SCENARIOS

This section evaluates the total suitability for viticulture in the part of Oltrepò Pavese region under projected future climate conditions. The total suitability index integrates three macro-factors climatic, soil, and topographic suitability to provide a comprehensive assessment of viticultural potential.

Four future climate scenarios were considered:

1-RCP 45 (2021–2050)

2-RCP 45 (2036–2065)

3-RCP 85 (2021–2050)

4-RCP 85 (2036–2065)

The methodological framework was identical to that used for the baseline assessment, ensuring full comparability between present and future conditions.

ACTUAL CONDITION TOTAL SUITABILITY RESULT

The final total suitability map integrates climatic, pedological, and topographical factors into a single representation of land potential for viticulture in the Oltrepò Pavese area.

Based on detailed GIS analysis of the raster (actual scenario), the land area distribution by suitability class is as follows:

S1 (Highly Suitable): 0.00%

S2 (Suitable): 18.18%

S3 (Moderately Suitable): 75.76%

N1 (Currently Not Suitable): 6.06%

N2 (Permanently Not Suitable): 0.00%

These results clearly show that the vast majority of the territory falls into the S3 (Marginally Suitable) class. A smaller portion of the land belongs to S2 (Moderately Suitable), highlighting areas with relatively better environmental conditions that offer more favorable.

The presence of N1 (Currently Not Suitable) areas, though only 6.06%, reflects zones where environmental constraints are too severe for viticulture under present conditions. Meanwhile, the absence of both S1 (Highly Suitable) and N2 (Permanently Not Suitable) confirms that there are neither highly optimal areas nor zones permanently excluded from viticultural use.

Overall, these findings suggest that while most of the landscape remains constrained within S3 (Marginally Suitable), targeted adaptation strategies could improve productivity, particularly in S2 (Moderately Suitable) zones where environmental conditions are comparatively more favorable.

Actual condition Total Suitability MAP (1991-2020):

FUTURE SCENARIOS TOTAL SUITABILITY RESULTS

The analysis of Total suitability for viticulture in the Oltrepò Pavese region under future scenarios reveals a challenging pattern characterized by a shift from the suitable zones and a concerning expansion of the N1 (Currently Not Suitable) class.

In the Actual Conditions:

The Actual Total suitability shows that the majority of the area is in marginally suitable, with a small portion currently not suitable. However, no areas are classified as S1 and N2 (Highly Suitable and permanently not suitable).

S2 (Suitable): 18.18%, S3 (Moderately Suitable): 75.76%, N1 (Currently Not Suitable): 6.06%.

Future Scenario:

Across all four future projections, there is a clear trend toward lower suitability. This is evidenced by a severe decline in S2, an increase in N1, and a resulting decrease in total suitable area (S2 + S3).

Scenario Extremes (Focus 2036–2065): In the latest period, the S2 class shrinks drastically to approximately 5%. The N1 class expands significantly, nearly doubling its current size, reaching 12.94% in the RCP 45 scenario and 9.90% in the RCP 85 scenario, Also the S3 class becomes the overwhelming dominant category, peaking at 85.30%.

Scenarios	S1	S2	S3	N1	N2
Actual	0	18.18	75.76	6.06	0
RCP45_21_50	0	16.83	74.60	8.57	0
RCP45_36_65	0	4.15	82.91	12.94	0
RCP85_21_50	0	8.73	81.27	10	0
RCP85_36_65	0	4.79	85.30	9.90	0

The expansion of the N1 (Currently Not Suitable) class across all future climate scenarios indicates a measurable and concerning decline in the region's overall viticulturally potential. The loss of suitable area requires strategic planning to mitigate adverse effects.

The transition in Total Suitability (S2+ S3) is clearly evident across all projections:

Actual Conditions: 93.94% suitability

RCP 45 (2021–2050): Suitability declines to 91.43%

RCP 85 (2021–2050): Suitability declines further to 90.00%

RCP 85 (2036–2065): Suitability is 90.10%

RCP 45 (2036–2065): Suitability reaches its lowest point at 87.06% (a loss of approximately 7% of suitable area from baseline).

This persistent decline, coupled with the severe shift of the remaining suitable area toward the S3 (Moderately Suitable) class, necessitates urgent and strategic adaptation measures.

Total Suitability RCP 45 (2021-2050):

Total Suitability RCP 45 (2036-2065):

Total Suitability RCP 85 (2021-2050):

Total Suitability RCP 85 (2036-2065):

ESTIMATION OF TOTAL SUITABILITY FOR GRAPEVINES IN OLTREPÒ PAVESE THROUGH A DATA-DRIVEN METHODOLOGY

INTRODUCTION

Besides the Multi-criteria modeling approach presented above classifies the studied territory of Oltrepò Pavese in suitable classes for actual climatic conditions, the modeled maps show no S1 (highly suitable) sectors, also in those territories traditionally vocated to viticulture as the north-eastern and central hilly area of Oltrepò Pavese (e.g. Versa, Scuropasso, Ghiaia di Montalto valleys). For these reasons, another model was developed for assessing grapevine total suitability in Oltrepò Pavese area, in order to obtain more confident results respect to the actual distribution of grapevines in this territory. This model was developed calibrating a data-driven approach developed to estimate the suitability of Oltrepò Pavese area to a crop suppletive of grapevines, namely the olive trees. The description of this method and the achieved results of its application follow. For more detailed information to the modeling approach, we refer to Bordoni et al. (2025).

This data-driven model was firstly developed to assess the possible evolution of the suitability of olive trees in a current marginal area as the Oltrepò Pavese, South located at northern edge of the typical geographical distribution.

The suitability model was developed using a database containing pixels with the response variable and an equal number of randomly selected pixels without either feature. The dataset was split into a training set (two-thirds) used to build the model and a test set (one-third) used for accuracy assessment. This process was repeated through 100 bootstrap iterations, generating 100 models whose mean predictions were used to create a total suitability map for the entire study area. Model accuracy was measured using the mean area under the ROC curve (AUROC) from all bootstrap models. Suitability probabilities were categorized into different classes of suitability. The model algorithm is based on Random Forest technique and considers geological, geomorphological and climatic predictors as input parameters to derive the relationship between total suitability to a crop over the considered territory.

The results indicate that future projections for olive trees—across short-term (2050), medium-term (2070), and long-term (2100) horizons—show an expansion of areas suitable for olive cultivation. This increased suitability is linked to rising air temperatures and a simultaneous decrease in frost days expected under future climate scenarios, which together enhance the potential for olive growth, particularly in regions at higher latitudes and elevations than those currently deemed most suitable. These findings provide a valuable basis for developing effective and sustainable land-use planning strategies and mitigation actions aimed at reducing climate-related impacts on agriculture. The approach presented here may therefore serve as a practical tool for evaluating present and future territorial suitability for olive cultivation.

The sensitivity analysis carried out to identify the most influential predictors in the selected data-driven model shows that, under current conditions in the Oltrepò Pavese area, suitability for olive trees is primarily driven by TEMP, FRD, SLH, TPI, SLA, and SLS. More than 97% of existing isolated olive trees and olive groves fall within the highly suitable class, which corresponds to hillslopes between 116 and 480 m a.s.l., with low to moderate steepness (generally below 21°) and aspects ranging from ESE to WSW (115–260°). High suitability is also associated with continuous hillslopes, whereas lower suitability emerges along ridges and at the floors of main river and creek valleys (TPI between -0.5 and 4.2). Among climatic factors, TEMP and FRD exert the strongest influence: highly suitable areas typically have average annual temperatures between 12.7 and 14.3 °C and fewer than 48 frost days per year.

The study also highlights how suitability patterns across the Oltrepò Pavese region evolve under different climate scenarios. All reconstructed scenarios show an increase in moderately and, more markedly, highly suitable areas. These changes are especially pronounced in the western and southern parts of the territory, while zones already classified as highly suitable under current conditions retain this classification in all future projections.

Consequently, the extent of highly suitable areas increases in every future climate scenario considered. In each time horizon, RCP 8.5 produces a larger gain in highly suitable areas compared to RCP 4.5. By 2050, moderately and highly suitable classes expand by 4% and 7% under RCP 4.5 and by 11% in both classes under RCP 8.5, corresponding to a reduction in marginally suitable areas of 11% and 22%, respectively.

The medium-term (2070) and long-term (2100) projections continue this trend. Highly suitable areas increase by 8–14% under RCP 4.5 and by 14–17% under RCP 8.5. Overall, 23–28% of the territory transitions to higher suitability classes in the medium and long term, particularly in the southern portion of the study area, where suitability is currently marginal.

Future suitability outcomes depend on projected changes in climatic predictors (TEMP, RAIN, FRD), assuming that geological, geomorphological, and botanical factors remain stable in the near future. To assess which climatic variables most strongly drive changes in suitability, the Spearman non-parametric correlation coefficient was calculated between the percentage increase in highly suitable areas and the variation in each climatic parameter under future scenarios.

Overall, the suitability scenarios produced using the data-driven approach—incorporating geological, geomorphological, climatic, and vegetational predictors—clearly demonstrate the influence of projected climate change on olive cultivation potential in the study area. Future projections indicate a consistent rise in suitable areas across all timeframes, with highly suitable zones potentially covering more than 40% of the territory by 2100, compared to 27% under present conditions. This improved suitability is strongly associated with rising temperatures and fewer frost days, enabling olive cultivation to expand into higher-elevation regions that are currently less favorable. More detailed results on the application of this model for the estimation of olive trees suitability in Oltrepò Pavese area are described in Bordoni et al. (2025).

Fig: Suitability to olive trees cultivation in Oltrepò Pavese, according to actual climatic conditions

TOTAL SUITABILITY RESULTS FOR ACTUAL AND FUTURE SCENARIOS

The results of the application of the proposed Random Forest model were reliable for the actual climatic conditions, since the average AUROC of the model was of 0.98. In the Actual Conditions the total suitability is clearly divided into two extremes. The region is currently dominated by S1 (Highly Suitable) areas, covering the majority of the suitable land, while a significant portion is classified as N2 (Permanently Not Suitable). Intermediate classes (S2 and S3) and N1 represent a minority of the area.

S1 (Highly Suitable): 51.54%

S2 (Suitable): 6.63%

S3 (Moderately Suitable): 2.95%

N1 (Currently Not Suitable): 4.31%

N2 (Permanently Not Suitable): 34.57%

The analysis of Total Suitability for viticulture in the Oltrepo Pavese region under future scenarios reveals a complex redistribution pattern. The trends are characterized by a dissolve of the currently polarized extremes (S1 and N2) and a significant shift toward intermediate suitability classes and the N1 (Currently Not Suitable) category.

Scenarios	S1	S2	S3	N1	N2
ACTUAL	51.54%	6.63%	2.95%	4.31%	34.57%
RCP45_21_50	19.96%	14.98%	28.51%	21.77%	14.78%
RCP45_36_65	4.37%	29.95%	33.29%	21.67%	10.72%
RCP85_21_50	12.53%	31.05%	31.52%	13.60%	11.31%

FUTURE SCENARIOS

Future projections show a major structural change in land suitability. The clearest trend is a sharp drop in both the best lands (S1) and the permanently unsuitable lands (N2). This suggests that while bad lands are improving (likely due to climate change), the highest quality areas are degrading. As a result, the region is shifting towards average suitability (S2, S3) and marginal lands (N1), especially in the northern sector of the area. Moreover, the most suitable classes tend to move towards the central sectors of Oltrepò Pavese area for all the future climatic scenarios.

Specifically, the S1 class drops dramatically from a baseline of 51.54% to as low as 4.37% in the RCP 45 scenario. Instead, S2 and S3 become the main categories for viticulture. Additionally, the N1 class grows significantly, rising from 4.31% to nearly 22%.

Actual Total Suitability

Total Suitability RCP 45 (2021-2050):

Total Suitability RCP 45 (2036-2065):

Total Suitability RCP 85 (2021-2050):

Total Suitability RCP 85 (2036-2065):

CONCLUSIONS

The application of the proposed methods for the evaluation of grapevine suitability in the selected contexts have given back contrasting results, especially for Oltrepò Pavese area. Moreover, it has to be taken into account that both the methods determine an environmental suitability, without considering any agronomical operations and practices which can improve the capability of cultivating grapevines also in contexts that have been modeled with low suitability or without suitability. We also highlight that the results of these models and the correlated maps cannot be used for the evaluation of the suitability at local scale (i.e. single field, hillslopes, little catchments), where more detailed studies has to be carried out to determine correctly the suitability towards grapevines

REFERENCES

- Adinolfi, M., Raffa, M., Reder, A. et al. Investigation on potential and limitations of ERA5 Reanalysis downscaled on Italy by a convection-permitting model. *Clim Dyn* 61, 4319–4342 (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-023-06803-w>
- Bucchignani, E., Montesarchio, M., Zollo, A.L., Mercogliano, P. (2016). High-resolution climate simulations with COSMO-CLM over Italy: performance evaluation and climate projections for the 21st century. *Int J Climatol* 36(2), 735–756. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.4379>.
- Giorgi, F. (1990). Simulation of regional climate using a limited area model nested in a general circulation model. *Journal of climate*, 3(9), 941-963.
- Hausfather, Z., Peters, G.P. (2020). Emissions – the 'business as usual' story is misleading. *Nature* 577, 618–620. <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-020-00177-3>.
- Hersbach, H. et al. (2020). The ERA5 global reanalysis. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.* 146, 1999–2049. <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.3803>.
- Prein, A. F., Langhans, W., Fosser, G., Ferrone, A., Ban, N., Goergen, K., ... & Leung, R. (2015). A review on regional convection-permitting climate modeling: Demonstrations, prospects, and challenges. *Reviews of geophysics*, 53(2), 323-361.
- Raffa, M., Reder, A., Marras, G. F., Mancini, M., Scipione, G., Santini, M., Mercogliano, P. (2021). VHR-REA_IT Dataset: Very High-Resolution Dynamical Downscaling of ERA5 Reanalysis over Italy by COSMO-CLM. *Data* 6(8), 88. <https://doi.org/10.3390/data6080088>.
- Raffa, M., Adinolfi, M., Reder, A. et al. Very High Resolution Projections over Italy under different CMIP5 IPCC scenarios. *Sci Data* 10, 238 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02144-9>

- Rockel, B., Will, A., Hence, A. (2008). The regional climate model COSMO-CLM (CCLM). *Meteorol. Z.* 17, 347–348. <https://doi.org/10.1127/0941-2948/2008/0309>.
- Scoccimarro, E. et al. Effects of tropical cyclones on ocean heat transport in a high resolution coupled general circulation model. *J. Clim.* 24, 4368–4384 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1175/2011JCLI4104.1>
- Tonietto, J., & Carbonneau, A. (2004). A multicriteria climatic classification system for grape-growing regions worldwide. *Agricultural and forest meteorology*, 124(1-2), 81-97.
- McMaster, G. S., & Wilhelm, W. W. (1997). Growing degree-days: one equation, two interpretations. *Agricultural and forest meteorology*, 87(4), 291-300.
- Huglin, M. P. (1978). Nouveau mode d'évaluation des possibilités héliothermiques d'un milieu viticole [climatologie]. *Comptes rendus des Séances de l'Académie d'Agriculture de France*, 64.
- Amerine, M. A., & Winkler, A. J. (1944). Composition and quality of musts and wines of California grapes.
- Bordoni, M., Gambarani, A., Giganti, M., Vivaldi, V., Rossi, G., Bazzano, P., Meisina, C., 2025. Present and projected suitability of olive trees in a currently marginal territory in the face of climate change: a case study from N-Italy. *Sustainability* 17, 1949. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17051949>
- Branas, J., Bernon, G., & Levadoux, L. (1946). A treatise on the elements of viticulture.
- Blanco-Ward, D., Queijeiro, J. G., & Jones, G. V. (2007). Spatial climate variability and viticulture in the Miño River Valley of Spain. *VITIS-GEILWEILERHOF-*, 46(2), 63.
- Thornthwaite, C. W., & Mather, J. R. (1951). The role of evapotranspiration in climate. *Archiv für Meteorologie, Geophysik und Bioklimatologie, Serie B*, 3, 16-39.
- ERSAF (2004). Carta dei suoli della Lombardia – scala 1:250.000.
- ERSAL (2001). I suoli dell'Oltrepò Pavese – scala 1:50.000
- FAO (1976). A framework for land evaluation; Chapter 3: Land suitability classifications. <https://www.fao.org/4/x15310e/x5310e00.htm>.
- US Department of Agriculture – Natural Resources Conservation Service (2022). Keys to Soil taxonomy <https://www.nrcs.usda.gov/sites/default/files/2022-09/Keys-to-Soil-Taxonomy.pdf>.
- IUSS Working Group WRB. (2022). World Reference Base for Soil Resources. International soil classification system for naming soils and creating legends for soil maps. 4th edition. International Union of Soil Sciences (IUSS), Vienna, Austria. https://wrb.isric.org/files/WRB_fourth_edition_2022-12-18.pdf.

APPENDIX: Spatial assessment of Pinot Noir in Oltrepò Pavese: analysis of the DOC/DOCG area and potential expansion in the Mountainous Oltrepò Region

This study represents an in-depth analysis building upon the outputs delivered within Research Module 1 of the NODES project, Spoke 6 (<https://www.ecs-nodes.eu/6-agroindustria-primaria>), Task 1.1 Data collection and needing. The objective is to integrate and further detail the knowledge concerning the distribution of the Pinot Noir variety within the area defined by the current Oltrepò Pavese DOC/DOCG boundaries, using as a starting point the dataset of vineyard surfaces derived from the SISCO database. The aim is to provide comprehensive information by combining multiple layers of data related to the characteristics of Pinot Noir vineyards, soil properties, and, more generally, the territorial features associated with the current production context of the Oltrepò area. The information produced will serve as a basis for forecasting the feasibility of extending the cultivated area to zones that are currently excluded, corresponding to the southern part of the mountainous Oltrepò Pavese. Following the methodology described in the subsequent chapters, the elaborated data will make it possible to verify the existence of analogies between the currently cultivated area (DOC/DOCG) and the one identified as a potential future opportunity for development, highlighting its peculiar or limiting aspects.

Introduction

The study is structured into two main phases: the first, dedicated to the analysis of the current conditions, explored the present distribution of Pinot Noir within the DOC/DOCG area of Oltrepò Pavese, using an existing zoning study as a reference. Through the integrated assessment of physical and territorial variables—altitude, slope, and aspect—the parameters that characterize already suitable areas, where the variety is successfully cultivated, were identified. In this first part of the study, additional insights were also developed regarding lithology and the territorial distribution of mapped landslide events.

Based on these findings, the second phase of the study applied the same criteria to the southern part of the Oltrepò Pavese, which falls outside the DOC/DOCG area, analysing agricultural surfaces suitable for possible viticultural development. The goal was to estimate future scenarios of vineyard expansion, matching the conditions that ensure high-quality production.

This methodology, which combines spatial analysis with comparative logic, provides a useful tool both for territorial planning and for deepening the understanding of the environmental conditions favourable to a grape variety of particular interest. Nevertheless, given the high variability of pedoclimatic contexts even within geographically close areas, it is important to emphasize the need to complement the territorial investigation with subsequent agronomic field verification, to validate the results obtained and to more effectively guide the establishment of any new vineyards.

Materials and Methods

The first part of the study, "*Current conditions: Territorial Analysis of the DOC/DOCG Area*", was based on the following input data:

- Agricultural parcels registered for the entire Oltrepò Pavese, downloaded from Sis.Co, the Agricultural Holdings Portal of Regione Lombardia, which is based on cadastral parcels

declared by farms in their farm registry file. This dataset represents the starting point for subsequent processing within the GIS (Geographic Information System)

- Geoportale Regione Lombardia: the cartographic service provided by Regione Lombardia, containing the region's official maps. For the purposes of this project, we used the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) with a 20x20 meter resolution, which defines the grid step of the territory in the corresponding raster.

Regarding the first dataset (Sis.Co), SHP files (Shapefiles) were obtained. A shapefile is considered a single dataset even though it is composed of multiple associated files. It is the most common geometric exchange format for vector-based spatial layers. A shapefile can consist of one of three geometry types—points, lines, or polygons—but cannot combine them within the same file; the choice depends on the specific analytical needs. In this study, we used polygon shapefiles, since the cadastral parcel perimeter, which represents an area, was the relevant unit of analysis.

For the second type of data, referring to the DEM, we considered another data format known as RASTER, which is defined as continuous data across the investigated territory. In our case, it describes the terrain in terms of elevation information every 20 meters (DEM 20x20 m). From the shapefile, we extracted all the areas and overlaid them with the RASTER data to obtain the tabular fields describing the attributes of the geometric dataset. The attribute table was then populated with data derived from the RASTER.

Each polygon is represented by one row in the attribute table of the shapefile. This table contains one column (Field) with a unique identifier for each geometric entity (single area), along with multiple fields describing the characteristics of each feature. These can be numerical (e.g., orthometric elevation, ISTAT code) or textual (e.g., the municipality to which the parcel belongs). Since in our case the entities correspond to cadastral parcels, the shapefile consists of polygons. The main procedural steps that enabled the territorial analysis are described below:

1. The first step in the analysis of the Pinot Noir variety consisted in identifying all parcels classified as the target variety, within the attribute table. Once the “variety” field was identified within the dataset, the parcels containing Pinot Noir were selected.
2. At this stage, a new shapefile with its corresponding attribute table was created, containing only the polygons previously selected for the variety of interest.
3. From the 20x20 DEM, two additional RASTER datasets were derived through spatial analysis: Slope (%) and Aspect (N-E-S-W).
4. A cartographic analysis of the territory was then carried out, integrating vector and raster data. For example, to each Pinot Noir polygon was associated information on elevation (m a.s.l.), slope (%), and aspect (N-E-S-W).

5. Once the attribute table had been populated with the information derived from the RASTER (see step 4), the cadastral parcels were classified according to the selected attributes. To achieve this, several classes of elevation, slope, and aspect were defined, based on previous suitability studies and structured to capture the complexity of the territorial distribution of the analysed grape variety.

The following steps illustrate the procedure that led to the creation of the maps and related graphs presented in the section “*Future Scenarios: Territorial Analysis of the Oltrepò Montano.*” The analysis was based on the following datasets, obtained from the Geoportal of Regione Lombardia and other cartographic sources:

1. DUSAF7: areas classified as “*permanent grasslands*” and “*arable land*” (Class 2) were selected, within the mountainous area of the Oltrepò Pavese.
2. Digital Elevation Model (DEM) with 20x20 m resolution: used for elevation analysis, from which slope and aspect rasters were derived.
3. Topographic Database (GPKG format) of the Province of Pavia: specifically, layers related to road network “*viabilità mista secondaria*” and “*viabilità principale*”.
4. Viabilità Agro-Silvo-Pastorale (VASP) in linear shapefile format.

The areas extracted from DUSAF7 cover very large surfaces. For this reason, unlike the analysis conducted in the DOCG area (where elevation, slope, and aspect parameters were directly interpolated for each Pinot Noir parcel), in this phase a different approach was adopted:

1. Creation of Homogeneous Territorial Units

- The elevation, slope and aspect raster which were derived from the DEM, were clipped to the areas extracted from DUSAF7 (“*arable land*” and “*permanent grasslands*”). The analysis area was the same for all three rasters.
- Each raster was then reclassified in line with the same elevation, slope and exposure classes adopted in the analysis of the current DOC/DOCG Pinot Noir area, producing three new reclassified rasters..
- Finally, the reclassified rasters were converted into polygon geometries with homogeneous values. This allowed for a better representation of territorial variability, moving from the 20x20 m raster grid to polygons defined according to the established elevation, slope, and aspect classes.

The steps described above are necessary because, while in the DOC/DOCG area the analysis units correspond to cadastral parcels designated for viticulture (which are immutable), in the Oltrepò Montano the reference units are defined based on elevation, slope, and aspect values derived

from the DEM. Without this reclassification, the analysis would be less precise, as the data would be distributed with greater heterogeneity. It should be noted that the slight variations observed in the surfaces, resulting from the methodology employed (transition from raster to vector), can be considered negligible both due to the minimal margin of discrepancy and in relation to the overall size of the analysed territory. Such differences do not compromise the overall robustness of the results obtained, nor the reliability of the evaluations conducted.

2. Accessibility Analysis

To evaluate the accessibility of the identified polygons from the perspective of the road network, the following procedure was followed:

- A 10-meter buffer was generated along the road axes, a distance considered suitable to represent the area with direct access for agricultural vehicles.

This buffer was applied both to the roads derived from the “Viabilità Agro-Silvo-Pastorale” (VASP) and to the “viabilità principale” e “viabilità secondaria” (VP/VMS) from the Topographic Database.

- Through a spatial intersection analysis (Select by Location), the “*permanent grassland*” and “*arable land*” areas directly connected to the road network were identified.

This selection allowed for the identification of readily cultivable land based on accessibility to the various parcels.

Final evaluation of suitable sites in the “*Oltrepò Montano*”:

To consolidate all previously collected information and to summarize the results of the “*current conditions*” assessment in relation to elevation, slope, and aspect, the following classification was adopted:

- Elevation score: CLASS 1: up to 600 m, considered suitable for Pinot Noir cultivation (based on the current conditions analysis); CLASS 2: 600–1000 m, considered potentially suitable particularly under a climate change perspective, albeit with some limitations; CLASS 3: above 1000 m, considered the upper limit for cultivation, where conditions must be assessed on a case-by-case basis.
- Slope score: CLASS 1/CLASSE 2: < 40%, considered suitable based on the analysis of the DOC/DOCG area; CLASS 3: > 40%, limiting due to operational difficulties in both access and vineyard planting, and therefore considered unsuitable.
- Aspect score: CLASS 1: E – S – W, considered suitable; CLASS 3: N, north-facing exposures were excluded due to limited solar radiation, especially in the mountainous areas considered.

By combining the three rasters, we obtained areas potentially suitable for vineyard expansion. Applying a 10-meter buffer along the road network allowed us to further restrict areas based on accessibility, resulting in surfaces with the most favourable topographic and access characteristics.

Current Conditions: Territorial Analysis of the DOC/DOCG Area

The analysis of cadastral parcels registered as Pinot Noir, covering approximately 3,712.7 ha and obtained from the “SisCO” portal, allowed a detailed examination of the current distribution of the grape variety within the DOC/DOCG area of Oltrepò Pavese. The study considered geo-lithological variables, the occurrence of landslide events and their implications for hydrogeological vulnerability, as well as the main elevation, slope, and aspect classes of the territory. The classes used were derived both from previous viticultural zoning and from criteria specifically developed to better represent the territorial peculiarities, aiming to characterize the suitability of Pinot Noir cultivation within the area of interest.

Distribution of Pinot Noir by Lithology

This section analyzes the distribution of Pinot Noir vineyard surfaces, totaling 3,712.7 ha within the DOC/DOCG area, in relation to nine main lithological classes identified in Oltrepò Pavese. These classes, composed of sedimentary and igneous rocks of various origins, represent heterogeneous groupings but share comparable mineralogical and structural characteristics. For the purposes of this study, a detailed geo-lithological distinction was not adopted; instead, a synthetic classification was used, suitable for the objectives of the territorial analysis.

The most represented lithological class is Class 8 (table below), consisting of marly and marly-sandy rocks, covering 1,142.9 ha, or 30.8% of the total surface. This is followed by Class 7, characterized by interstratified rocks with alternating marls, calcareous marls, and shales, covering 809 ha (21.8%). Another significant class is that of interstratified rocks with alternating marls, sandstones, and shales, covering 544 ha, or 14.7%.

The remaining lithological classes (1, 2, 4, 5, and 9) are less represented, with a uniform distribution averaging approximately 242 ha each. In summary, the distribution of vineyard surfaces highlights the predominant role of marly and sandy soils, which collectively account for the largest portion of cultivated areas, while the other classes are less extensive and more fragmented across the territory.

Classi litologiche	Definizione	Superficie (ha)	Superficie (%)
Classe 1	Arenarie, conglomerati, ofioliti	241,6	6,5%
Classe 2	Argille e argilliti	298,8	8,0%
	Argille con inclusi lapidei poligenici argilliti		

Classe 3	Detrito clasto sostenuto	1,9	0,1%
	Detrito matrice sostenuto		
Classe 4	Ghiaia, sabbia e limo	198,3	5,3%
Classe 5	Marne gessose	159,0	4,3%
Classe 6	Rocce interstratificate: alternanza di marne, arenarie e argilliti	544,4	14,7%
	Rocce interstratificate: arenarie intercalate con argille		
Classe 7	Rocce interstratificate: alternanza di marne, marne calcaree e argilliti	809,0	21,8%
	Rocce interstratificate: marne calcaree con intercalazioni argillose		
Classe 8	Rocce marnose e marnoso arenacee	1142,9	30,8%
Classe 9	Sabbia, limo e argilla	316,5	8,5%

Distribution of Pinot Noir in Landslide-Affected Areas

This chapter examines the distribution of Pinot Noir vineyard surfaces (3,712.7 ha within the DOC/DOCG area) in relation to the occurrence of landslide phenomena. Landslides were classified into different types based on their dynamic state: active, reactivated, suspended, quiescent, stabilized, and relic. This classification allows distinguishing situations with varying levels of risk and monitoring needs, to assess potential mitigation measures.

Data analysis shows that of the 3,712.7 ha planted with Pinot Noir, 47.3% (approximately 1,754.3 ha) are located in landslide-prone areas. This confirms the high hydrogeological risk in Oltrepò Pavese and the widespread territorial fragility. The distribution of landslides reveals that 37.4% of the landslide-affected area is classified as active, reactivated, or suspended, corresponding to the highest-risk zones. A larger portion, 51.3%, falls into the quiescent category, indicating a condition of potential instability, where risk remains elevated even in the absence of active slides. Stabilized landslides account for approximately 10% of the landslide-affected area and require on-site investigation to assess the effectiveness of implemented mitigation strategies.

This information is essential for integrating territorial planning guidelines, enabling farmers and competent authorities to define targeted interventions tailored to the specific conditions of the slopes, thereby reducing hydrogeological risk without compromising the agricultural use of the land.

Tipologia di frana	Superficie (ha)	Superficie (%)
Attivo/riattivato/sospeso	656,9	37,4%
Quiescente	900,5	51,3%
Stabilizzato	175,0	10,0%
Relitto	2,7	0,2%
Non determinato	19,1	1,1%

Altitude Class Distribution of Pinot Noir Vineyards

The analysis of vineyard distribution by altitude classes allowed an assessment of the presence of Pinot Noir in relation to elevation. For the creation of the thematic map, vineyard surfaces were divided into plain, low and mid-hill, high-hill, and mountainous categories. This classification was then contextualized within the DOC/DOCG area of Oltrepò Pavese, enabling the identification of six altitude classes corresponding to the different elevations across the territory.

The distribution analysis of the 3,712.7 ha of Pinot Noir highlights a heterogeneous presence throughout the DOC/DOCG area of Oltrepò Pavese. The northern part of the area shows a higher concentration of vineyards in the lower altitude classes (<150 m and 150–250 m), whereas in the southern zones, vineyard surfaces are more prevalent at higher elevations, following a gradient reflecting the local orography. The first three classes (<150, 150–250, and 250–350 m a.s.l.) cover a total of 3,166.6 ha, corresponding to 85.3% of the vineyard area, indicating the predominance of plains and mid-hill. The higher classes (450–550 m and >550 m a.s.l.), although less extensive, still represent 3.3% of the total area, equal to 122 ha, including 6.6 ha in the mountainous category (>550 m). These data suggest that, even at higher elevations, pedoclimatic and microclimatic conditions can support high-quality viticulture, highlighting the relevance of further investigation into exposure, soil, and other local variables for each vineyard.

Classi altimetriche	Altitudine (m s.l.m.)	Superficie (ha)	Superficie (%)
Classe 1	<150	1388,1	37,4%
Classe 2	150 - 250	887,2	23,9%
Classe 3	250 - 350	891,3	24,0%
Classe 4	350 - 450	424,0	11,4%
Classe 5	450 - 550	115,4	3,1%
Classe 6	>550	6,6	0,2%

Slope Class Distribution of Pinot Noir Vineyards

The territorial analysis of Pinot Noir considered the slope of the hillsides, calculated from the 20x20 m DEM raster for each parcel. Subsequently, vineyard surfaces were divided into five slope classes, defined based on technical choices made during vineyard planting and the standard mechanized vineyard operations.

The analysis of Pinot Noir vineyard distribution in relation to slope shows a generally more homogeneous pattern compared to altitude. Most vineyard areas fall within classes 2 (10–20%) and 3 (20–35%), which together cover approximately 3,201.9 ha, corresponding to 86.2% of the total. In the north-northeastern part of the area, which is geographically flatter, class 3 (medium slopes, 20–35%) is notably present, while class 1 (<10%) remains significant, consistent with the presence of flat land.

The steeper slope classes, 4 (35–40%) and 5 (>40%), occupy smaller areas, totalling 102.3 ha, and are not strictly associated with the higher altitudes in the southern part of the area. These steep areas present significant operational and management challenges, which require further investigation to understand the strategies currently employed by winegrowers to ensure high-quality viticulture even under limiting conditions.

Classi di pendenza	Pendenza (%)	Superficie (ha)	Superficie (%)
Classe 1	<10	408,5	11,0%
Classe 2	10 - 20	2031,1	54,7%
Classe 3	20 - 35	1170,8	31,5%
Classe 4	35 - 40	56,4	1,5%
Classe 5	>40	45,9	1,2%

Distribution of Pinot Noir by Aspect

Vineyard planting decision is a complex process that requires an integrated evaluation of multiple factors. Soil analysis is crucial, as its chemical and physical composition, pH, nutrient content, and drainage capacity directly influence the selection of grape varieties and rootstocks suited to the specific conditions. Variety and rootstock choice is closely linked to pedoclimatic conditions and the vineyard's production and winemaking objectives. Planting density, i.e., the number of vines per hectare, must be calibrated based on the vigour of the varieties, soil characteristics, and agronomic practices, since higher density can improve grape quality but increases competition for resources. Among all these factors, slope aspect plays a key role because slope orientation and inclination affect solar radiation, vine phenology, microclimatic conditions, and the occurrence of phytosanitary issues.

Analysis of vineyard parcels by altitudinal classes showed that vineyards in the Oltrepò Pavese DOC/DOCG area extend up to 550 m a.s.l. Consequently, the distribution of vineyard areas was further examined according to slope aspect. In the map and in the table shown below, north-facing slopes are coloured blue, east-facing green, south-facing red, and west-facing light brown; Pinot Noir parcels are represented as black polygons. The assessment highlights a predominance of vineyards with west and east exposures, totalling 1,450.4 ha and 979.2 ha, respectively. These exposures, particularly at higher altitudes, optimize net solar radiation absorption, enhance photosynthesis, more favourable ripening conditions, and lower risk of spring frosts. North-facing slopes account for only 11.8% of the Pinot Noir vineyard area, corresponding to 437.7 ha.

Esposizione dei versanti	Superficie (ha)	Superficie (%)
EST	979,2	26,4%
SUD	844,4	22,7%
OVEST	1450,4	39,1%
NORD	437,7	11,8%

Future Scenarios: Territorial Analysis of the Oltrepò Montano

The analysis presented in this section aims to identify available land in the southern area of Oltrepò Pavese, a territory which has remained largely unused for viticultural purposes but shows promising development potential considering the new scenarios imposed by climate change. Lands classified as “*permanent grasslands*” and “*arable land*” in the DUSAF7 dataset were considered, while forests and categories unsuitable for agricultural development were excluded. After defining the available areas, expressed in hectares, a further assessment was carried out to select plots exhibiting specific characteristics.

To ensure methodological consistency and comparability, the same criteria applied to the DOC/DOCG area were adopted, to identify similarities and differences between the two territorial contexts. The analysis, conducted following the methodology described in the Materials and Methods chapter, utilized a 20x20 m Digital Elevation Model (DEM), from which altitude, slope, and aspect RASTER layers were derived. The territorial assessment was carried out using the classifications previously defined for altitude, slope, and aspect, which are key parameters for evaluating viticultural potential in relation to current climatic conditions. In some cases, additional classes were introduced where not present in the DOC/DOCG area previously analysed.

Adopting the same classification enables comparison with the DOC/DOCG area and the assessment of the feasibility of quality viticulture in the Oltrepò Montano. The information obtained provides a tool for validating potential new vineyard plantings and determining whether this territory provides topographic, altimetric, and microclimatic conditions compatible with an area already recognized for its viticultural suitability.

DUSAF7-Identified Surfaces

The first step of the territorial analysis involved selecting the areas classified as Level 2 – “*Agricultural Areas*”, and more specifically Level 21 – “*arable land*” and Level 23 – “*permanent grasslands*”, according to the DUSAF7 land use classification, within the mountainous territory of the Oltrepò Pavese. This selection resulted in a total of 7,101 ha, of which 5,130.3 ha were classified

as “*arable land*” and 1,970.7 ha as “*permanent grasslands*”. The aim was to identify agricultural areas, which may be potentially convertible to viticulture.

For this reason, all land-use levels unsuitable or already committed to permanent cropping systems were excluded. In particular, the following levels were not considered:

- level 1 – “aree antropizzate”;
- level 3 – “territori boscati e ambienti seminaturali”;
- level 4 – “aree umide”.

In addition, although included under agricultural areas, Level 22 – “*permanent crops*” was not considered. This class is defined as “*colture non soggette a rotazione che forniscono più raccolti e che occupano il terreno per un lungo periodo prima dello scasso e della ripiantatura*”, already occupied by stable tree crops. Within this category, the following were excluded: 221 – “*vigneti*”, 222 – “*frutteti e frutti minori*”, 223 – “*oliveti*”, and 224 – “*arboricoltura da legno*”.

These categories, characterized by perennial crops, require established agronomic management and do not represent areas immediately available for vineyard conversion or already under vine cultivation. The decision to focus on arable land and permanent grasslands therefore allowed for a more precise delimitation of surfaces with greater land-use flexibility, providing a more realistic framework of the potential areas for viticultural expansion in the Oltrepò Montano.

Distribution of DUSAF Areas by Elevation Classes

As previously described, the analysis of DUSAF7 areas (“*arable land*” and “*permanent grassland*”, 7,101.0 ha) was divided into elevation classes following the study of Pinot Noir in the DOC/DOCG area, integrating Classes 7 (600–1000 m a.s.l.) and 8 (1000–1550 m a.s.l.) to account for elevation ranges not represented in the “*current conditions*” analysis. In the Oltrepò Montano, most of the available surfaces are concentrated in the mid- to high-elevation ranges, particularly in Class 7 (2,773.7 ha, 38.9%), followed by Class 5 (1,850.2 ha, 26%) and Class 4 (1,070.8 ha, 15%). Lower hill areas (Class 3, 250–350 m) are marginal (233.1 ha, 3.3%), while Class 6 (550–600 m) accounts for 795.2 ha (11.2%). Class 8 (high mountain, 1000–1550 m) covers a smaller share (404.8 ha, 5.7%), currently unsuitable, yet potentially valuable under future climate scenarios. Overall, the distribution shows a marked concentration between 450 and 1000 m a.s.l., reflecting the geomorphological features of the area.

A comparison with DOC/DOCG data indicates that while Pinot Noir is predominantly cultivated below 600 m a.s.l., in the Oltrepò Montano the surfaces within this threshold (Classes 3, 4, 5, and 6) amount to 3,949.3 ha, distributed as follows: Class 3 – 233.1 ha (3.3%), Class 4 – 1,070.8 ha (15.0%), Class 5 – 1,850.2 ha (26.0%), Class 6 – 795.2 ha (11.2%). These results highlight the presence of extensive areas that are elevation-compatible with viticulture, suggesting potentially favourable conditions for Pinot Noir and other grape varieties. Compared with the DOC/DOCG area, where vineyards are concentrated at lower elevations and decrease above 550 m, the Oltrepò Montano offers significant development potential in terms of this parameter, which should be assessed in relation to local microclimatic and soil conditions.

Classi altimetriche	Altitudine (m s.l.m.)	Superficie (ha)	Superficie (%)
Classe 1	<150	/	/
Classe 2	150 - 250	/	/
Classe 3	250 - 350	233,1	3,3%
Classe 4	350 - 450	1070,8	15,0%
Classe 5	450 - 550	1850,2	26,0%
Classe 6	550 - 600	795,2	11,2%
Classe 7	600 - 1000	2773,7	38,9%
Classe 8	1000 - 1550	404,8	5,7%

Distribution of DUSAF Areas by Slope Classes

Following the same approach used for the analysis of Pinot Noir vineyard distribution in the DOC/DOCG area, the potentially convertible areas classified as “arable land” and “permanent grassland” (DUSAF7) were divided into five slope classes: Class 1 – Flat (<10%), Class 2 – Low slope (10–20%), Class 3 – Moderate slope (20–35%), Class 4 – Limiting slope (35–40%), and Class 5 – Critical slope (>40%). This subdivision, based on recognized technical and operational criteria in viticulture, considers the feasibility of mechanized operations and the challenges related to erosion and slope stability.

In the Oltrepò Montano, the distribution of areas shows a clear concentration in Classes 2 and 3, which together cover 87.6% of the total available surface, amounting to 3,217.6 ha (45.6%) and 2,959.2 ha (42%), respectively. Class 1 (<10%) covers 588.8 ha (8.4%), Class 4 (35–40%) 162.3 ha (2.3%), and Class 5 (>40%) 123.6 ha (1.8%), as reported in Table 10.

The predominance of areas with slopes between 10% and 35% (Classes 2 and 3) outlines a favourable scenario for vineyard conversion, allowing the establishment of mechanizable plantings with “rittochino” or “girapoggio” row systems. Although marginal, areas in Classes 4 and 5 are still present and would require specific adjustments during planting, such as terracing and embankments, with associated additional costs.

Overall, the slope class analysis confirms a substantial availability of morphologically suitable surfaces for viticulture, to be considered alongside with additional factors such as slope exposure and accessibility for agricultural machinery.

Classi di pendenza	Pendenza (%)	Superficie (ha)	Superficie (%)
Classe 1	<10	588,8	8,4%
Classe 2	10 - 20	3217,6	45,6%
Classe 3	20 - 35	2959,2	42,0%
Classe 4	35 - 40	162,3	2,3%
Classe 5	>40	123,6	1,8%

Distribution of DUSAF Areas by Aspect

Slope aspect is a key factor for agronomic suitability, influencing vineyard microclimatic conditions, light availability, and thermal conditions—factors particularly relevant in the hilly and mountainous areas of the Oltrepò Pavese, which are characterized by high morphological heterogeneity. An analysis of the DUSAF7 “permanent grassland” and “arable land” surfaces

shows a prevalence of west-facing slopes (32.5%, 2,297.7 ha), followed by south (24.4%, 1,726.5 ha) and east (18.5%, 1,310 ha).

North-facing surfaces are surprisingly well represented (24.5%, 1,731.2 ha), despite lower light exposure and reduced heat accumulation, which negatively affect photosynthetic activity and ripening. This can be explained by the fact that many north-facing areas are located at lower elevations with milder temperatures. An additional explanation is that these areas, being grasslands and arable land, support crops that are less demanding in terms of light and temperature.

Overall, the presence of north-facing surfaces reflects territorial and economic constraints rather than deliberate technical choices aimed at optimizing production. Unlike altitude distribution, dominated by the 450–600 m and 600–1,000 m classes, slope orientation is more balanced. In this context, the widespread presence of south- and west-facing surfaces can help compensate for less favorable altitudes, as observed in the DOC/DOCG vineyard areas.

Esposizione dei versanti	Superficie (ha)	Superficie (%)
EST	1310,0	18,5%
SUD	1726,5	24,4%
OVEST	2297,7	32,5%
NORD	1731,2	24,5%

Accessibility in relation to the road system

For the assessment of viticulture potential in the DUSAF 7 areas of the Oltrepò Montano (7,101 ha), road accessibility is a key discriminating factor, crucial for vineyard management operations. In a territory characterized by high altimetric and morphological variability, the road network directly affects the feasibility of using agricultural machinery, logistical efficiency, and the economic sustainability of new plantings.

Data from the Topographic Database of the Province of Pavia were used, covering main roads (paved and with good load-bearing capacity) and secondary mixed roads (local roads, often unpaved but accessible to agricultural machinery), along with the Agro-Forestry-Pastoral Road dataset (VASP), considering classes II, III, and IV as suitable for tractors and small farm vehicles. Accessibility was estimated by creating a 10 m buffer along the road axes and selecting DUSAF 7 areas ("permanent grasslands" and "arable land") intersecting this buffer, totalling 5,795.5 ha.

Most of the accessible surfaces are served by main roads (89.9%, 5,212.9 ha), followed by secondary roads (8.5%, 493.4 ha) and VASP (1.5%, 89.2 ha). Although marginal, VASP roads are particularly relevant in mountainous zones, allowing access with specialized agricultural machinery. Overall, the analysis indicates that road accessibility does not constitute a structural constraint to

viticultural expansion, thanks to the adequate infrastructure and the presence, albeit limited, of areas reachable via VASP, which offer opportunities for development even in disadvantaged areas.

Classificazione Reticolo Stradale	Superficie servita (ha)	Superficie servita (%)
Viabilità principale	5212,9	89,9%
Viabilità mista secondaria	493,4	8,5%
VASP 	89,2	1,5%

Final assessment of suitable areas

To identify areas potentially suitable for the expansion of quality viticulture in the Oltrepò Montano, an integrated assessment of the main physical-territorial variables was carried out: altitude, slope, and aspect. The objective was to identify areas with the most favourable topographic conditions for Pinot Noir cultivation, considering only those portions of land that align with current vineyards in the DOC/DOCG area.

From an altimetric perspective, areas below 600 m a.s.l. (Class 1) were considered suitable; areas between 600 and 1000 m (Class 2) were regarded as potentially cultivable, albeit with some reservations related to thermal-radiative conditions and growing season length; areas above 1000 m (Class 3) were excluded. Regarding slope, areas under 40% (Classes 1 and 2) were deemed suitable, while steeper slopes (Class 3) were excluded due to operational limitations and erosion risk. In terms of aspect, areas facing East, South, and West (Class 1) were considered suitable, whereas North-facing slopes (Class 3) were excluded.

The combination of the three raster layers—altitude, slope, and aspect—through spatial analysis in ArcGIS produced a synthetic map identifying 4,841.4 ha of potentially suitable land, excluding all areas classified as Class 3 for any of the three factors. Subsequently, the suitability of these areas was further assessed in relation to road accessibility using the Topographic Database of the Province of Pavia and generating a 10 m buffer along the road axes. The intersection between the road buffer and the suitable DUSAF 7 polygons narrowed the selection to 3,889.1 ha, representing areas that meet both topographic and technical-operational accessibility criteria.

For a more detailed overview, suitable areas were subdivided by altitudinal band: 2,280.4 ha below 600 m a.s.l., consistent with the predominant altitude of current Pinot Noir vineyards in the DOC/DOCG area, and 1,608.7 ha between 600 and 1,000 m a.s.l., representing “pioneering” zones at the upper altimetric margins, with growing potential in the context of climate change adaptation. This final synthesis highlights zones that, in terms of altitude, slope, aspect, and accessibility, are suitable for the potential expansion of quality viticulture in the Oltrepò Montano.

References

- Mariani L., Minelli R. (2008). Guida All'utilizzo della denominazione di origine Pinot Nero nell'Oltrepo Pavese" Consorzio Tutela Vini Oltrepo Pavese (2008) Editore Tipografia Succursali Diani e Maffi
- ERSAF (2004). Carta dei suoli della Lombardia – scala 1:250.000.
- ERSAL (2001). I suoli dell'Oltrepò Pavese – scala 1:50.000
- FAO (1976). A framework for land evaluation; Chapter 3: Land suitability classifications. <https://www.fao.org/4/x15310e/x5310e00.htm>.
- US Department of Agriculture – Natural Resources Conservation Service (2022). Keys to Soil taxonomy <https://www.nrcs.usda.gov/sites/default/files/2022-09/Keys-to-Soil-Taxonomy.pdf>.
- IUSS Working Group WRB. (2022). World Reference Base for Soil Resources. International soil classification system for naming soils and creating legends for soil maps. 4th edition. International Union of Soil Sciences (IUSS), Vienna, Austria. https://wrb.isric.org/files/WRB_fourth_edition_2022-12-18.pdf.
- Boni A., Braga G., Bellinzona G., Beatrizotti G. (1965) *"Foglio 59 Pavia. Carta Geologica d'Italia in scala 1:100000 (II Ed.)"*. Servizio Geologico d'Italia, Roma
- Braga G., Braschi G., Calculli S., Caucia F., Cerro A., Coleselli F., Grisolia M., Piccio A., Rossetti R., Setti M., Spallaro A., Soggetti F., Veniale F. (1985) *"I fenomeni franosi nell'Oltrepo Pavese: Tipologie e cause"* in *"Geologia Applicata e Idrogeologia 20 parte II"* (1985) pp. 621-666